

persist

positive energy districts
driven by citizens

Deliverable D3.1

Energy Flexibility as a Service (EFaaS) scenarios from Verdal public buildings, where the role of final consumers/prosumers is enabled actively in the energy market

Work Package 3: Design of energy flexibility solutions

Deliverable type: Report

Lead beneficiary: Østfold University College (HiØF)

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List of Abbreviations and Symbols

Term	Meaning / description	Unit/note
ARX	Auto-regressive model with exogenous inputs	–
ASHRAE	American Society of Heating, Refrigerating and Air-Conditioning Engineers	–
$\hat{b}_{i,h}$	Estimated non-heating baseline for building i at hour-of-day h	kW
\hat{b}_{i,H_t}	Warm-hour baseload (non-heating baseline) for building i at the hour-of-day H_t	kW
BiasPct $_i$	Mean bias of SHL estimate (building i)	%
$C_{i,t}$	Cold-hour mask (1 = heating allowed) for building i , hour t	–
CIN	Net investment costs (capital investment)	–
COP	Coefficient of performance	–
CPQR	Change point quantile regression	–
CPR	Change point regression	–
CPLR	Change point linear regression	–
D3.1	Deliverable 3.1 of the PERSIST project	–
DHN	District heating network	–
DHW	Domestic hot water	–
DSF	Demand-side flexibility	–
DSO	Distribution system operator	–
DUT	Driving Urban Transitions (funding programme)	–
Δ En	Change in energy use (energy savings)	–
EB	Energy bill	–
EB E	Energy bill for electricity	–
EB Q	Energy bill for heat (district heating)	–
EBC	Energy in Buildings and Communities Programme	–
ECFIF	Energy cost flexibility improvement factor	–
EF	Energy flexibility	–
EFaaS	Energy Flexibility as a Service	–
EH	Electric heating	–
EUI	Energy use intensity	kWh/m ² ·year
GA	Genetic algorithm	–
g	building cluster (group) index (e.g., a school cluster, or kindergarten cluster)	–
$h_{i,t}$	True (submetered) SHL for building i , hour t	kW
$\hat{h}_{i,t}$	Estimated SHL for building i , hour t	kW
$\tilde{h}_{i,t}^{\text{base}}$	the baseline/reference space-heating load profile for building i at hour t	kW
$h_{i,t}^{\text{flex}}$	Activated (flexible) space-heating load trajectory for building i at hour t	kW
HDH _{i,t}	Heating degree-hours for building i , hour t	°C·h
HiØF	Østfold University College (Norway)	–
HMM	Hidden Markov model	–
HP	Heat pump	–
HPSS	Synergetic heat and power supply system	–
HS	Heat storage (thermal storage)	–
HVAC	Heating, ventilation and air conditioning	–
HWCB	Hot water circulation based	–
HWT	Hot water tank (thermal storage tank)	–
ICA	Independent component analysis	–
ICA-PLR	Hybrid independent component analysis–piecewise linear regression method	–
IEA	International Energy Agency	–
IQR	Interquartile range	–
l_i	Lag window in mask (building i)	h
LP	Linear programming	–

MAE	Mean absolute error	–
MAE_i	Mean absolute SHL error (building i)	kW
MSAB	Multi-story apartment building	–
N	Number of evaluation time steps	–
nMAE	Normalized mean absolute error	–
$nMAE_i$	Normalized MAE (building i)	%
NHL	Non-heating load (non-space-heating electricity use)	kW
NPV	Net present value	–
P10	10th percentile (lower quantile)	–
P2H	Power-to-heat	–
P50	50th percentile (median)	–
PED	Positive Energy District	–
PERSIST	“Positive EnerGy diStrIctS driven by ciTizens” project	–
PG	Power grid	–
PHPR	Total rated power of installed heat pumps	–
PI	Prediction interval	–
PLR	Piecewise linear regression	–
PP	Payback period	–
PPVR	Total rated power of installed PV panels	–
PV	Photovoltaic (solar PV system)	–
PWTR	Total rated power of installed wind turbines	–
$r_{i,t}$	residual above the warm hour baseload	kW
R_t	The portfolio residual vector at time t , the stacked the residuals from all buildings.	kW
R^2	Coefficient of determination	–
R_i^2	Coefficient of determination for building i	–
RFR	Random forest regression	–
$RMSE_i$	Root-mean-square SHL error (building i)	kW
RPS	Renewable power sources	–
RTU	Riga Technical University	–
S_i	Seasonal scaling factor (building i)	–
SCR	Self-consumption rate	–
SFR/SSR	Self-sufficiency rate	–
SHL	Space-heating load (actual or estimated)	kW
T_t	Outdoor air temperature at hour t	°C
$T_{b,t}$	Balance temperature for building i	°C
TDC	Total daily costs	–
θ_i	Mask parameter vector for building i (τ_i, l_i, s_i, w_i)	–
Θ_i	Optimized parameter set (estimated/calibrated for building i)	–
τ_i	Base temperature in mask (building i)	°C
TOWST	Time-of-week-temperature-solar model	–
UPV	Universitat Politècnica de València (Spain)	–
$U_{i,t}, L_{i,t}$	Time-varying upper & lower bounds on the <i>feasible heating load</i> for building i at hour t	–
UTCN	Technical University of Cluj-Napoca (Romania)	–
W	Optimization window	–
W_s	Set of “warm” hours that heating demand is negligible	–
W_h	A “warm” hour subset at hour-of-day that heating demand is negligible	–
W_i	Weekend/holiday factor (building i)	–
WP	Work Package	–
WT	Wind turbine	–
$y_{i,t}$	Total electricity for building i , hour t	kW
$z_{i,t}$	Normalized / standardized variable for building i , hour t	–

Executive Summary

This deliverable presents the progress of Work Package 3 (WP3), “Design of energy flexibility solutions”, in the PERSIST project. It describes the development and first implementation of a common technical framework for Energy Flexibility as a Service (EFaaS) and applies this framework to Verdal municipality. In the project proposal, Deliverable D3.1 is defined as “EFaaS scenarios on Verdal municipality”. In this report, that objective is met through a detailed case study of Verdal’s municipal public-building portfolio, which acts as the primary test site. The work is based on hourly data from 1 January to 31 December 2024.

The original description of D3.1 is focused on EFaaS scenarios for apartment buildings in Verdal. Due to data availability, metering coverage, and local priorities, the implementation concentrates on the public-building portfolio in Verdal, Norway. The EFaaS framework developed here is explicitly designed to be transferable and will be applied to residential and mixed-use buildings as additional data become available in Tasks 3.2-3.4 and in Deliverable D3.2.

The main technical case in D3.1 is therefore the public-building portfolio of Verdal municipality in Norway. The dataset covers 22 buildings organized into four groups: six schools (S1-S6), five kindergartens (K1-K5), five office buildings (O1-O5), and six institutions (I1-I6). For each building, hourly main-meter electricity data for 2024 (8,784 hours per building) are combined with hourly weather data and calendar variables. Five buildings (K1, S6, O4, O5, I6) have separate sub-meters for space-heating load (SHL) and provide reference data for calibration and validation. Verdal’s cold climate with long heating seasons, together with municipal ownership and clear operating schedules, makes this portfolio a representative and practical case for developing and testing EFaaS concepts.

Figure 1: Overview of the D3.1 EFaaS methodological framework

As shown in Figure 1, the first technical pillar of the D3.1 is a hybrid ICA-PLR (Independent Component Analysis–Piecewise Linear Regression) framework for SHL disaggregation. The framework addresses the practical fact that SHL is rarely submetered at scale in municipal or residential portfolios, even though it is the main lever for heating-related demand response in cold climates. The method uses a temperature- and schedule-based mask to select hours where space heating is expected, applies ICA to masked residuals across buildings to extract a latent component with heating-like behavior, and then fits a heating-degree-hour (HDH) PLR model for each building to re-scale and interpret this component. The PLR step yields building-specific parameters

such as balance temperature and response lag and enforces physically plausible temperature responses. Temporal consistency is improved by applying ramp-rate constraints and blending day and night estimates. Validation against submetered SHL in five reference buildings shows that the hybrid ICA-PLR approach achieves hourly coefficients of determination R^2 of around 0.82 with nMAE in the range 18-22 %. Aggregation to weekly values in the heating season increases R^2 to approximately 0.89-0.95. These results indicate that the method reproduces the main temperature dependence and temporal structure of SHL in the Verdal portfolio. Table 1 gives the energy consumption and SHL details of the buildings used in the ICA-PLR load disaggregation and analysis.

Table 1: Portfolio consumption

Portfolio headline numbers (2024)	
Total electricity	6.95 GWh
Estimated SHL	2.91 GWh
SHL share for a year	42 % of total
SHL share during Dec-Feb months	54% of total
SHL shares in buildings with high heating demand (Dec-Feb)	55-73% of total

The second technical pillar is an uncertainty-aware framework for quantifying heating-demand flexibility from the estimated SHL time series and weather data. This framework builds an ensemble baseline for SHL that combines change-point linear regression, change-point quantile regression, and a time-of-week-temperature-solar model, with a day-of adjustment step to align the baseline with the current operating state. A non-intrusive occupancy proxy is derived from NHL, its short-term variability, and calendar variables. Simple autoregressive models with exogenous inputs are used to estimate effective thermal time constants that describe building heat storage and response. Empirical safety envelopes and ramp limits are derived from historical SHL levels and ramps. On this basis, a chance-constrained, energy-neutral optimization problem is solved to construct capacity–duration curves and availability metrics at building and portfolio level, indicating how much SHL can be curtailed or shifted over specified durations and temperature bands while keeping comfort risk within predefined limits.

Together, these two pillars form a measurement-based pipeline that starts from hourly smart-meter data and produces, for each building and for the portfolio, uncertainty-aware flexibility envelopes for electric space heating. For Verdal’s 22 public buildings in 2024, total electricity use is approximately 6.95 GWh, of which about 2.91 GWh, or 42 %, is estimated to be SHL on an annual basis. During winter months (December–February), the SHL share increases to around 54 %, and some buildings reach winter SHL shares between roughly 55 and 73 % of total electricity use. Institutions and the largest schools dominate the upper tail of SHL shares and account for most of the winter SHL, while offices and kindergartens exhibit lower SHL fractions but clear morning warm-up and evening setback patterns. Capacity–duration analysis confirms that short events of one to two hours enable larger relative reductions than longer events, and that available flexibility is highest under moderate cold conditions (for example, outdoor temperatures between about 0 and -10 °C). Under more extreme cold, flexibility is reduced due to tighter comfort margins and limited heating capacity.

On the scenario side, D3.1 translates these technical results into EFaaS scenarios for Verdal public buildings. Three main EFaaS scenario templates are defined. The first is a morning peak-shaving

scenario for day-use buildings, in which schools, kindergartens, and offices adjust pre-heating and warm-up schedules on winter weekdays to reduce SHL during the main morning peak. The second is an evening and weekend setback optimization scenario, in which evening setpoints and weekend SHL baselines in day-use buildings are tightened and coordinated to limit unnecessary heating in low-occupancy periods. The third is a controlled modulation scenario for institutions, in which 24/7 or extended-operation buildings provide smaller but more frequent upward and downward adjustments around their baseline within clearly defined comfort and service constraints. These templates are designed to be compatible with local distribution system operator needs, time-of-use tariffs, and possible virtual power plant configurations, while maintaining indoor comfort and service quality.

The work reported in D3.1 is the outcome of contributions from PERSIST partners. HiØF leads WP3 and is responsible for the methodological framework, SHL disaggregation, and flexibility quantification for the Verdal public buildings. RTU team contributes renewable-integration and technology optimization studies that use SHL profiles and flexibility envelopes to evaluate portfolios of photovoltaics, heat pumps, biomass boilers, and thermal storage, and to examine business models in which flexibility and EFaaS services are part of the value proposition. In parallel, RTU team develops and tests a methodology for a synergetic heat and power supply system (HPSS) in a Latvian multi-story apartment building, demonstrating how the quantified flexibility indicators can be used in equipment sizing, control strategies, and economic assessment for residential EFaaS applications (both section “3.3.8 Parameters used for evaluation of flexibility” and section “3.4.2 Methodology for equipment selection and control of a synergetic HPSS” are developed by the RTU team). HSLU-IET applies the supervised method of load disaggregation and flexibility framework to Swiss residential and mixed-use buildings as a first test of transferability beyond the Norwegian municipal context. Other partners, including UTCN, UC, and EHU, plan to use the common framework and indicators from D3.1 to support national case studies, district-level transition planning, impact assessment, and exploitation activities in their respective living labs.

D3.1 also recognizes current limitations and outlines the next steps. The present analysis is restricted to public buildings in Verdal and focuses on hourly-resolution flexibility; submetered SHL validation is available only in a subset of buildings. These limitations largely reflect data availability and the staged approach defined for WP3. Next steps, to be reported in D3.2 “Building power exploitation” and in related WPs, include extending the methodological pipeline to apartments and residential buildings in other living labs, refining and validating flexibility estimates as additional data become available, integrating EFaaS scenarios into virtual power plant and energy-community designs, and combining the technical results with socio-economic, policy, and citizen-related insights from WP2, WP4, WP5, and WP6.

1 Introduction

Buildings are a major driver of energy use and greenhouse-gas emissions in Europe [1]. In the European Union, the building stock accounts for a large share of final energy demand and energy-related emissions, mainly due to space heating, cooling, and domestic hot water (DHW) production [2]. Improving the energy performance and operational flexibility of buildings is therefore essential for achieving long-term climate and energy-system targets [3].

Positive Energy Districts (PEDs) have been proposed as one pathway to decarbonize urban areas. A PED is commonly defined as an urban area or group of connected buildings that combines high energy efficiency, local renewable generation, and active interaction with surrounding energy networks to reach a net-zero or net-positive annual energy balance at district scale [4], [5], [6]. PED concepts emphasize not only energy balances but also system integration, spatial planning, governance, and citizen participation [5], [6].

Within PEDs and similar concepts, demand-side flexibility (DSF) in buildings is increasingly recognized as a system resource. The IEA EBC Annex 67 [7] defines energy flexibility in buildings as the ability of a building or group of buildings to adjust their energy demand and on-site generation over time, for example by shifting, shedding, or modulating loads, while maintaining occupant comfort and indoor environmental quality [8]. Such flexibility can reduce peak loads, support the integration of variable renewable generation, and defer network reinforcement and generation investments [9], [10]. In practice, building flexibility is closely related to demand response and to emerging local flexibility markets, in which distribution system operators (DSOs) and other actors procure flexibility from distributed energy resources, including flexible buildings, distributed storage, and electric vehicles [9].

In this deliverable, Energy Flexibility as a Service (EFaaS) denotes the set of technical, organizational, and contractual arrangements through which building level flexibility is quantified, aggregated, and offered as a service to system operators, aggregators, and local energy communities [4], [11]. EFaaS concepts require robust methods to (i) estimate SHL and NHL from available measurements, (ii) characterize flexibility potential with quantified uncertainty, and (iii) link these technical indicators to technology portfolios, operational strategies, and business models.

The PERSIST project (“Positive EneRgy diStrIctS driven by ciTizens”) addresses these challenges by combining technical, social, and governance perspectives across several European living labs [11]. Verdal municipality in Norway is one of the main living labs and focuses on the interaction between public buildings, residential areas, and the local distribution grid in a cold-climate context. Parallel activities in Latvia, Switzerland, Romania, Portugal, and Spain provide complementary methodological and case-study contributions that will use and extend the EFaaS framework introduced in this deliverable.

In cold-climate regions, SHL is typically the dominant end use in non-industrial buildings, and in countries such as Norway, a large share of this heating demand is met by electricity using direct electric heaters, heat pumps, and electric boilers, sometimes in combination with biomass or district-heating systems [12], [13], [14]. Hourly electricity and weather data therefore provide a natural basis for monitoring, modelling, and controlling SHL in support of grid services and energy-efficiency objectives. This deliverable report develops and applies a measurement-based EFaaS framework that uses such hourly data to estimate SHL and NHL, quantify heating-demand flexibility, and design EFaaS scenario templates for municipal and, in later work, residential buildings.

1.1 WP3 objectives and position of D3.1

Work Package 3 (WP3), *Design of energy flexibility solutions*, aims to develop and demonstrate methods and tools for exploiting demand-side flexibility in PEDs, with a particular emphasis on EFaaS. WP3 runs over the full project duration (M1-M36) and is led by Østfold University College (HiØF) [11]. It is structured into four tasks:

- T3.1: Characterization of flexibility, which identifies consumption patterns, classifies flexibility resources, and estimates virtual power and storage integration options;
- T3.2: Prosumer data acquisition, which deploys IoT and communication technologies to collect high-resolution data and enable real-time monitoring;
- T3.3: Virtual power plant concepts, which aggregates distributed resources and defines control and market-participation strategies; and
- T3.4: Feasibility of power exchange and energy communities, which analyses technical, regulatory, and economic conditions for local energy exchange and community-based flexibility services [11].

Figure 2: Task T3.1 and T3.2 in work package 3 (WP3)

Figure 2 summarizes the roles of Tasks T3.1 and T3.2 in the present deliverable. D3.1 is the first major output of WP3 and is described in the Description of Action as “EFaaS scenarios on Verdal municipality” [11]. In practice, the scope has been refined in agreement with project partners to

focus on the first implementation step on Verdal's municipal public building portfolio, where high-quality hourly metering and weather data are available for 2024.

Within this adjusted scope, the role of D3.1 is to:

1. Establish a common, measurement-based framework for characterizing SHL, NHL, and heating-demand flexibility using hourly data;
2. Present and validate a hybrid ICA-PLR method for SHL disaggregation against submetered references in a subset of buildings.
3. Develop an uncertainty-aware flexibility quantification methodology that yields capacity–duration curves and availability metrics; and
4. Develop methodology for technology and equipment selection for synergetic heat and power supply system (by RTU team).

This framework constitutes the technical core of WP3 and provides a reference that partners can reuse in cross-regional analyses, technology-portfolio studies, and EFaaS business-model development.

1.2 Scope and structure of the document

This deliverable documents the development of the EFaaS framework in PERSIST, with a primary focus on Verdal's public building portfolio and methodological contributions that can be transferred to other living labs. Section 2 describes the Verdal case and the underlying datasets. It introduces the local context, summarizes the municipal public-building portfolio (clusters, floor area, heating systems), and specifies the 2024 hourly electricity, weather, and calendar data used in this deliverable. The section also outlines the main pre-processing and quality-control steps and presents key descriptive energy profiles.

Section 3 presents the common EFaaS technical framework and applies it to Verdal. Section 3.1 defines data requirements and basic concepts. Section 3.2 introduces the hybrid ICA-PLR method for disaggregating whole building hourly electricity into SHL and non-heating load (NHL) and reports the Verdal disaggregation results, validation, and recommended reporting practice. Section 3.3 describes the flexibility-quantification framework based on baseline ensembles, occupancy proxies, thermal time constants, safety envelopes, and chance-constrained optimization, and applies it to derive flexibility indicators for the Verdal portfolio. Within this section, section 3.3.8 (Parameters used for evaluation of flexibility) was developed by the RTU team. Section 3.4 links these SHL and flexibility outputs to technology and portfolio design. It summarizes the RTU methodology developed for equipment selection and control of a synergetic heat and power supply system (HPSS) and presents a Latvian multi-story apartment building case study.

Section 4 concludes the deliverable by synthesizing the main findings from Sections 2 and 3.

2 Norway: Verdal public buildings and data

This section introduces the Verdal living lab, the municipal public-building portfolio used in D3.1, and the datasets that underpin the SHL and flexibility analysis. It also summarizes the main preprocessing steps applied before the methodological framework in Section 3 is implemented.

2.1 Case context and data

As shown in Figure 3, Verdal is a municipality in Trøndelag county in central Norway. The region has a cold-temperate climate with a long heating season; climate assessments for Norway and climate normals for central Norway indicate mean January temperatures below 0 °C and frequent sub-zero days from late autumn to early spring [15], [16]. Under these conditions, space heating is typically the dominant end use in non-industrial buildings [12], [13], [14]. As in other Norwegian municipalities with similar climates, electricity is the main energy carrier for space heating in non-residential buildings, supplied primarily through direct electric heaters, heat pumps, and electric boilers, sometimes in combination with biomass or district-heating systems [12], [13], [14].

Figure 3: Verdal Municipality in Norway

Verdal municipality owns and operates a portfolio of schools, kindergartens, administrative offices, and institutional buildings that together form a coherent and controllable group of loads within the local distribution grid [11]. These public buildings are essential for municipal service provision and include typical day-use buildings (schools, kindergartens, and offices) as well as 24/7 or extended-operation institutions. They represent a non-trivial share of local electricity demand and exhibit well-defined operating schedules, which makes them a suitable test bed for the EFaaS framework developed in PERSIST [11].

In the PERSIST project, Verdal serves as one of the main living labs for WP3, with a focus on how public buildings and, in later stages, residential areas can be operated as flexible resources while maintaining service quality [9]. The public-building portfolio provides a realistic test case for the EFaaS framework because metering infrastructure is already in place, hourly data are available for a full year, and the municipality is an engaged stakeholder in discussions on flexibility, tariffs, and potential business models [11].

2.2 Building portfolio overview

The dataset used in this deliverable covers 22 municipal buildings in Verdal. The buildings are grouped into four functional clusters. The clusters are as following; six schools (S1-S6), five kindergartens (K1-K5), five office buildings (O1-O5), and six institutions (I1-I6). The institutional group includes medical and rehabilitation centers and cultural facilities. The buildings differ in floor area, construction period, and heating system. Floor areas range from small kindergartens to large schools and institutions with several thousand square meters of heated area. The main heating technologies are direct electric panel heaters, heat pumps, and bio-pellet boilers with water-based distribution. In several buildings, central systems are supplemented by local panel heaters in specific zones. This mix of building types and heating systems is typical of Norwegian municipal building stocks and is relevant for EFaaS because heating technology, envelope quality, and building size all influence SHL and flexibility potential. Table 2 summarizes the main characteristics of the 22 buildings, including cluster, floor area, primary heating system, total electricity consumption in 2024, specific electricity use (kWh/m²), and construction year. Buildings are grouped by cluster to support later analysis of SHL patterns and flexibility. The 22 building sites are referenced by code S/K/O/I + index (for example, S6 denotes School 6). The five buildings equipped with SHL sub-metering and used for calibration and validation are identified in Table 2 under the “Validated” column.

Table 2: Buildings in scope and validation flags (2024)

Code	Type	Heating system	validated?	Notes	Annual consumption (2024) - kWh	Consumption (kWh)/ sqm	Construction year
S1	School	geothermal and electric	No	Day-use	265,194	77.67	2020
S2	School	Direct electric	No	Day-use	520,021	177.91	1950
S3	School	Direct electric	No	Day-use	212,736	165.42	1970
S4	School	Direct electric	No	Day-use	721,165	146.07	1977
S5	School	Bio pellets boiler, water	No	Day-use	570,570	99.72	1970 *
S6	School	Direct electric	Yes	Day-use	910,900	199.98	1970
K1	Kindergarten	Direct electric	Yes	Day-use	144,492	168.21	1980
K2	Kindergarten	Direct electric	No	Day-use	46,010	84.89	1980 *
K3	Kindergarten	Direct electric	No	Day-use	79,539	232.57	1950
K4	Kindergarten	Direct electric	No	Day-use	6,802	20.54	1992 *
K5	Kindergarten	Direct electric	No	Day-use	43,532	56.76	2018
O1	Office	Direct electric	No	Day-use	299,272	202.21	1970
O2	Office	Heat pump	No	Day-use	309,416	107.74	1970 *
O3	Office	Direct electric	No	Day-use	160,331	73.21	1970 *
O4	Office	Direct electric	Yes	Day-use	547,267	121.61	1980 *
O5	Office	Heat pump	Yes	Day-use	275,971	168.28	1998
I1	Institution	Direct electric	No	24/7	148,630	232.23	1970
I2	Institution	Direct electric	No	24/7	326,861	149.95	1970
I3	Institution	Bio pellets boiler, water	No	24/7	539,438	114.17	2000
I4	Institution	Direct electric	No	24/7	92,417	115.52	2018
I5	Institution	Heat pump	No	24/7	512,165	177.51	1950
I6	Institution	Direct electric	Yes	24/7	217,508	191.64	1950

**Buildings that are renovated recently (between 2000 to 2024)*

For each building, hourly electricity consumption is later decomposed into SHL and NHL using the hybrid ICA-PLR method described in Section 3.2.

2.3 Data sources and monitoring period

The analysis in D3.1 is based on hourly data for the full calendar year 2024. For each of the 22 buildings, the following data streams are used:

- Hourly main-meter data, provided by the municipal energy management system “Entelios”. Main-meter readings are recorded as hourly energy (kWh). Then, converted to average hourly power (kW) by dividing by $\Delta t = 1h$; kW is used throughout unless stated otherwise.
- Hourly outdoor weather data for the Verdal area, including at least air temperature and, where available, relative humidity, wind speed, precipitation, and a proxy for global solar irradiance.
- Calendar variables, including hour of day, day of week, month, and Norwegian public and school holidays, used to distinguish typical working days, weekends, and holiday periods.

Figure 4 summarizes the annual electricity use and energy intensity of each building, and marks with an asterisk the five sites equipped with separate sub-meters for SHL: K1 (kindergarten), S6 (school), O4 and O5 (offices), and I6 (institution). These submetered SHL time series provide the reference data used to calibrate and validate the hybrid ICA-PLR disaggregation method introduced in Section 3.2.

Figure 4: Annual electrical energy demand of the public buildings

2.4 Pre-processing and quality control

All time series data were converted to a consistent time zone (local Oslo time) and checked for completeness and consistency. Timestamps were made strictly monotonic, and duplicate entries were merged by averaging. Where needed, main-meter electricity data were resampled or aggregated to hourly resolution so that each building has a single observation per hour for the full year 2024. Short gaps in the electricity data were filled using conservative interpolation procedures designed to preserve peak and valley behavior, especially during winter periods when SHL is most relevant. Longer gaps were flagged and excluded from model fitting and validation. Weather variables were aligned to the same hourly grid and inspected for outliers. When short gaps occurred in the weather series, they were filled using neighboring values or simple persistence rules.

Outlier detection was applied to the electricity and weather data using robust statistics, for example based on the median and median absolute deviation. Values identified as clear instrumentation errors were either corrected, when a plausible replacement could be inferred, or flagged and excluded from the SHL disaggregation and flexibility modelling. These pre-processing and quality-control steps are essential to avoid bias and spurious patterns in the subsequent analysis.

2.5 Data & energy profiles analyzed

Before applying the methodological framework in Section 3, it is useful to summarize the overall electricity use in the portfolio. The dataset covers 22 public buildings organized into four clusters: six schools, five kindergartens, five offices, and six institutions. Hourly main-meter electricity is analyzed from 1 January to 31 December 2024 (8,784 hours per building) and is joined to hourly weather and calendar variables. Five sites include space-heating sub-meters as given in Table 3. Figure 5 illustrates typical weekday diurnal profiles according to building cluster. Weekday cycles show sharp increases in total electricity consumption between approximately 06:00 and 08:00 and clear evening setbacks in all day-use buildings (schools, kindergartens, and offices). Weekend demand falls close to a baseline level in these building types, whereas institutions, most of which operate 24/7, display steadier profiles. Some institutional sites, such as I3, show lower average weekend demand, indicating reduced occupancy or activity. The Figure 5 highlights Monday morning recovery peaks and Friday afternoon tapering, which point to practical opportunities for pre-heating and setback adjustments. For a concise overview of the datasets used in the analysis, Table 3 summarizes the main data sources, volumes, and key fields.

Table 3: Raw datasets used (2024)

Dataset	Population / Volume	Resolution	Key fields	Notes
Main electricity meters	22 buildings × 8,784 h = 193,248 rows	Hourly, 2024	kW (total), timestamp	Local-time alignment; duplicates averaged.
SHL sub-meters (validation)	5 sites × 8,784 h = 43,920 rows	Hourly, 2024	kW (space heating)	K1, S6, O4, O5, I6 are used for calibr./ validation.
Weather	8,784 h (joined to all sites)	Hourly, 2024	Outdoor T (°C), RH, wind, precipitation, solar irradiance	From nearest station, used in masking and PLR refit.
Calendar/occupancy	8,784 h (per site)	Hourly, 2024	Hour-of-day, weekday/weekend, month, holidays; day-use vs 24/7	Build the cold-hour and schedule masks.

Figure 5: Mean hourly electricity consumption by building cluster (whole year data).

Figure 6 shows average winter weekday electricity demand profiles by building cluster (schools, kindergartens, institutions, offices) for December–March. In all day-use clusters, there is a pronounced morning ramp between approximately 06:00 and 08:00, followed by a daytime plateau and an evening setback. This pattern is strongest in schools and offices, where median demand roughly doubles between the night minimum and the morning peak in January and February, reflecting simultaneous space-heating recovery and start-up of lighting, ventilation, and equipment. In kindergartens, the morning increase is also clear but slightly earlier and narrower, consistent with shorter operating hours and smaller buildings; demand declines more rapidly after 16:00 as occupancy drops. Offices exhibit a similar pattern to schools but with slightly lower relative night-time baseload and more gradual evening reduction.

The monthly traces in said figure indicate that winter demand is highest in January and February, with December somewhat lower and March clearly reduced across all clusters, in line with the seasonal heating requirement. For schools and offices, the difference between January–February and March is most visible in the height of the morning and midday plateau rather than in the night baseload. Institutions display a different profile: night-time consumption remains comparatively high and diurnal swings are smaller, reflecting 24/7 or extended operation. Their morning increase is modest, and evening setbacks are limited, although some sites (for example I3) show lower demand on winter weekdays in March, suggesting reduced heating needs and/or lower occupancy. Taken together, the profiles in said figure highlight three robust features relevant for EFaaS design: (i) concentrated morning warm-up periods in day-use buildings, (ii) clear evening setback

opportunities in schools, kindergartens, and offices, and (iii) steadier but smaller modulation potential in institutions due to their higher night baseload and continuous service requirements.

Figure 6: Average winter weekday load profile (hour-of-day) by cluster (building type).

Among the 22 buildings analyzed, five sites are equipped with submetered SHL, providing hourly reference data for calibration and validation. These five buildings cover all major clusters which include one kindergarten (K1), one school (S6), two office buildings (O4, O5), and one institutional building (I6) and are indicated by hatched bars in Figure 7a and by the “Validated” flag in above Table 2. To evaluate generalization, the submetered dataset has the following details:

Calibration and validation: The five submetered datasets (K1, S6, O4, O5, I6) were used for calibration and validation to tune cold-hour mask parameters (e.g., base temperature θ_0 , seasonal and weekend scaling factors, and lag window L) via random search and local refinement. Also, it is used for out-of-sample testing of the final parameter set and for computing portfolio-level performance metrics (R^2 , MAE, nMAE, Pearson correlation coefficient r) without further re-training.

Figure 7: Description of building types and outdoor temperature in the area (a) Building counts by category of types; hatched bars denote building(s) with submetered SHL, (b) Year-built ranges (old-new) (1950–2020), (c) Floor-area ranges (min–max) (331–5,722 m²), (d) 2024 outdoor-temperature at the nearest station; line = monthly mean, band ≈ 10th–90th percentile; shaded region marks the excluding summer period (excluding June–August) used in analyses.

Figure 7 provides physical information including construction year, floor area, etc. overview of the building stock and in climatic context. Figure 7(a) shows the number of buildings in each functional cluster and highlights the distribution of submetered sites. Figures 7(b) and 7(c) illustrate the spread in construction year and floor area, respectively. Schools and institutions tend to be larger, often in the range 3,000–5,700 m², and several were built or substantially renovated after 2000, whereas kindergartens are smaller (approximately 300-1,000 m²) and some offices occupy intermediate sizes. This heterogeneity in size and construction period implies differences in envelope performance, installed heating systems, and internal gains, all of which influence SHL profiles and flexibility potential. Figure 7(d) shows the 2024 outdoor temperature profile at the nearest weather station: monthly mean temperatures remain below or close to 0 °C from December to March, while the shaded band (approximately 10th-90th percentile) indicates frequent sub-zero conditions outside the summer months. The highlighted excluding summer period (September-May) corresponds to the main heating season used in several subsequent analyses.

3 The EFaaS Framework and Verdal results

This section presents the methodological framework used in WP3 to estimate SHL from hourly whole-building electricity data and to quantify heating-demand flexibility at building and portfolio level. The framework is designed to be applicable across PERSIST living labs, with local adaptations depending on data availability and context. Sub-sections 3.2 and 3.3 report the Verdal implementation developed by HiØF (3.3.8 contributed by RTU team), while Section 3.4 shows how the same outputs can be used for technology and portfolio optimization, with a detailed Latvian case study contributed by RTU.

3.1 Data requirements and basic concepts

The framework assumes access to the following time-series and metadata for each building or aggregated load:

- Hourly electricity consumption at the main meter.
- Hourly outdoor weather data, at minimum dry-bulb air temperature, and, where available, global solar irradiance, wind speed, relative humidity, and precipitation.
- Calendar variables, including hour of day, day of week, month, and local public and school holidays, used to distinguish typical working days, weekends, and holiday periods.
- Optional SHL sub-meters for a subset of buildings, used as reference data for calibration and validation.

Temperature dependence is represented using heating-degree hours (HDH) [17]. For each hour t ,

$$\text{HDH}_t = \max \{0, T_{b,i} - T_t\}, \quad (1)$$

Where, $T_{b,i}$ is the building-specific balance temperature and T_t is the outdoor air temperature at hour t . HDH is used in PLR models, which relate SHL to temperature in different operating regimes (for example, below and above the balance temperature). The balance temperature and an effective response lag (capturing delays between outdoor temperature changes and SHL response) are treated as building-specific descriptors and are used in both the disaggregation and flexibility-quantification steps.

3.2 Hybrid ICA-PLR load disaggregation and heating load in Verdal

This section describes the ICA-PLR method and results on public buildings in Verdal.

3.2.1 The ICA-PLR load disaggregation method

Direct sub-metering of SHL is rarely available at portfolio scale, even though heating is often the dominant controllable end use in cold climates. Non-intrusive load disaggregation and blind-source-separation techniques, including Independent Component Analysis (ICA), have therefore been explored to separate heating and NHL uses from aggregate meters [18], [19], [20], [21].

Purely data-driven methods, however, can be sensitive to noise and may violate basic physical constraints if they are not guided by temperature, occupancy, [22], [23] and thermal-inertia [24] considerations [25], [26].

The hybrid ICA-PLR framework developed in this deliverable combines multi-building ICA with heating-degree-hour (HDH) change-point regression [27], [28] and simple dynamical constraints to estimate hourly SHL and NHL from main-meter data. Figures 8 and 9 give an overview of the pipeline and of the core disaggregation module. The method is designed to be reproducible in other living labs and to remain compatible with standard baseline-modelling practice (e.g. variable base degree-day change point models and ASHRAE Guideline 14) [29], [27], [28].

Figure 8: The hybrid ICA-PLR method stepwise workflow

Step 1: Data cleaning and feature construction

Hourly main-meter electricity data for the $B = 22$ public buildings are combined with outdoor temperature, other meteorological variables, and calendar indicators (hour of day, day of week, month, weekend/holiday flag). Standard pre-processing steps include de-duplication of time stamps, resampling to an hourly grid, and conservative gap-filling for short missing segments, which follows common practice in smart-meter based building analysis and studies [30], [18], [31], [23]. After the preprocessing described in Section 2.4, each hourly observation is represented by a feature vector. For each building i and hour t , the feature vector:

$$\mathbf{x}_{i,t} = (y_{i,t}, T_t, \mathbf{x}_t^{\text{meteo}}, H_t, D_t, M_t, W_t) \quad (2)$$

is obtained, where T_t is outdoor air temperature x_t^{meteo} collects additional meteorological variables (e.g., wind, humidity), and H_t, D_t, M_t, W_t are hour-of-day, day-of-week, month, and a weekend/holiday indicator and $y_{i,t}$ is the aggregated load.

Step 2: Cold / warm hour classification and masking

Since SHL is strongly temperature-driven and subject to thermal inertia, the analysis focuses on hours when heating is expected to be active. For each building group g (schools, kindergartens, offices, institutions), a group-specific balance temperature τ_g , seasonal scaling factors, and weekend modifiers are defined. Day-level “cold” and “mild” types are determined from the number of hours above τ_g , and a rolling minimum of recent outdoor temperature is used to represent thermal storage effects [24], [22]. This yields a binary mask $c_{i,t} \in \{0,1\}$ that identifies heating-plausible hours for building i . The mask is applied both upstream (for constructing the residual matrix used in ICA) and downstream (for gating the final estimate), a strategy that reflects standard temperature-based pre-screening in change-point models [21] - [23], [32] - [33].

For each building cluster g (schools, kindergartens, offices, institutions), a provisional balance temperature τ_g and simple schedule rules are used to identify hours when space heating is expected. This yields a binary cold-hour mask

$$c_{i,t} = \mathbf{1}\{T_t \leq \tau_g\} \cdot s_{i,t}, \quad (3)$$

where $\mathbf{1}\{\cdot\}$ is the indicator function and $s_{i,t} \in \{0,1\}$ encodes typical occupied hours for cluster g (day-use versus 24/7 operation). Hours with $c_{i,t} = 1$ are treated as “heating-plausible” in the subsequent steps.

Step 3: Warm-hour baseload estimation

To prevent non-heating end uses from being misclassified as SHL, a baseline profile is constructed from “warm” hours in which heating can be assumed negligible [20], [23], [32]. For each building i and hour of day h , the warm-hour baseload $\hat{b}_{i,h}$ is estimated as a robust statistic (mean or low quantile) of $y_{i,t}$ over hours with high outdoor temperatures, with separate treatment for day-use and 24/7 institutions. A non-heating baseload is estimated from warm hours, where electric space heating is assumed to be negligible. Let τ^* be a high temperature threshold and the set of warm hours W_s are as follows

$$W_s = \{t: T_t \geq \tau^*\}$$

For each building i and clock hour h , the baseline is

$$\hat{b}_{i,h} = \frac{1}{|W_h|} \sum_{t \in W_h} y_{i,t}, \quad W_h = \{t \in W: H_t = h\}, \quad (4)$$

While, W_h is a warm-hour subset at hour-of-day that heating demand is negligible for day-use buildings; for 24/7 institutions the mean can be replaced by a low percentile to reduce the influence of occasional peaks. This baseline represents NHL under warm conditions.

For hours classified as cold, residual above the warm hour baseload $r_{i,t}$ are computed as deviations from the warm-hour baseload:

$$r_{i,t} = y_{i,t} - \hat{b}_{i,H_t}, \text{ for } c_{i,t} = 1. \quad (5)$$

Stacking $r_{i,t}$ across buildings yields portfolio residual vectors $R_t = [r_{1,t}, \dots, r_{B,t}]^T$. Each building's residuals are standardized to zero mean and unit variance over all cold hours. where H_t is the hour-of-day index. Only residuals for hours with $c_{i,t} = 1$ ("cold-hour" mask) are used in the subsequent ICA step. This warm-hour baseload approach is consistent with previous disaggregation work that separates weather-sensitive and weather-insensitive components [23], [33], [34]. Figure 9 presents the core disaggregation part of the proposed hybrid ICA-PLR framework.

Figure 9: flowchart of the core disaggregation part of the proposed hybrid ICA-PLR framework

Step 4: ICA on cold-hour residuals

The cold-hour residuals $r_{i,t}$ from all buildings are stacked into a matrix $\mathbf{R} \in \mathbb{R}^{B \times T_{\text{cold}}}$, standardized per building to zero mean and unit variance, and decomposed using the FastICA algorithm [35], [36]. FastICA with whitening is applied to the standardized residual matrix,

$$\mathbf{R} = \mathbf{A} \mathbf{S} \quad (6)$$

where, \mathbf{A} is the mixing matrix and the rows of \mathbf{S} are statistically independent components. A heating-like component is selected using a physics-guided score favoring components that (i) are negatively correlated with outdoor temperature and (ii) correlate with short-horizon heating-degree dynamics (based on Eq. (1)) [19]. For each building i , an ICA-based heating signal $h_{i,t}^{\text{ICA}}$ is reconstructed from the selected component and mapped back to physical units (kW), then clipped to $[0, y_{i,t}]$ to respect power limits.

Step 5: HDH-PLR refinement (synthesis)

To anchor the ICA estimate in a physically consistent temperature response, a building-specific balance temperature $T_{b,i}$ is identified on a discrete grid by minimizing total-load error. Using this $T_{b,i}$, degree-hours becomes

$$\text{HDH}_{i,t} = \max(0, T_{b,i} - T_t), \quad (7)$$

which is a building-specific variant of Eq. (1). A simple change-point (CPLR) regression is then fitted for each building,

$$\hat{h}_{i,t}^{\text{PLR}} = \beta_{0,i} + \beta_{1,i} \text{HDH}_{i,t} + \beta_{2,i} [\text{HDH}_{i,t} - \kappa_i]_+, \quad (8)$$

where $[\cdot]_+ = \max(\cdot, 0)$ and κ_i is a hinge point that captures increased heating sensitivity under very cold conditions (i.e., the extra term activates only when $\text{HDH}_{i,t} > \kappa_i$). In this equation, $\hat{h}_{i,t}^{\text{PLR}}$ is the PLR-based estimate of the space-heating load for building i at hour t (kW); $\text{HDH}_{i,t}$ is the heating degree-hours at building i and hour t ($^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}$); $\beta_{0,i}$ is the building-specific intercept (kW); $\beta_{1,i}$ is the baseline SHL sensitivity to HDH (kW per ($^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}$)); $\beta_{2,i}$ is the additional sensitivity beyond the hinge (kW per ($^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}$)); and κ_i is the building-specific hinge point in degree-hours ($^{\circ}\text{C}\cdot\text{h}$). The model is trained on hours with non-zero heating in the submetered buildings; for non-metered buildings, $h_{i,t}^{\text{ICA}}$ is used as a proxy target.

The ICA and PLR estimates are combined using time-of-day weights, with a higher weight on PLR during morning recovery hours and a higher weight on ICA during daytime and evenings. After applying a simple ramp-rate limiter to avoid unrealistic hour-to-hour changes, the final SHL estimate is

$$\hat{h}_{i,t} = c_{i,t}(\alpha_{i,t} h_{i,t}^{\text{ICA}} + (1 - \alpha_{i,t}) \hat{h}_{i,t}^{\text{PLR}}), \quad (9)$$

where, where $c_{i,t}$ is the cold-hour (heating-allowed) mask and $\alpha_{i,t} \in [0,1]$ is the blending weight that determines how much the final heating estimate relies on the ICA-based heating signal versus the PLR-based estimate and $\hat{h}_{i,t}$ is the final estimated space-heating load (kW) for building i at hour t . NHL is obtained as $y_{i,t} - \hat{h}_{i,t}$.

Step 6: Calibration (optimization) and transfer to non-metered buildings

The mask parameters (τ_g , schedule rules), balance temperatures $T_{b,i}$, and blending weights $\alpha_{i,t}$ are calibrated on the five submetered buildings by minimizing a composite objective combining normalized MAE, explained variance, and bias. Cluster-level median parameter sets are then used for the remaining buildings, ensuring consistent treatment across the portfolio while preserving building-type differences.

This stepwise hybrid ICA-PLR framework yields hourly SHL and NHL time series for all 22 Verdal buildings, together with building-level descriptors (balance temperature, HDH slopes, mask parameters) that are subsequently used in the flexibility quantification framework in Section 3.3.

3.2.2 Verdal SHL disaggregation results

Figure 10 presents the monthly submetered SHL for K1, O4, O5, I6, and S6 (bars) together with the average outdoor temperature (dashed line), showing a clear inverse relationship, with high

heating use from December to March, very low values from June to August, and a gradual increase during spring and autumn. I6 exhibits the highest and most persistent winter load, consistent with near continuous operation, O4 and O5 lie in an intermediate range with a visible non-heating baseline, and K1 and S6 display the most pronounced shoulder season transitions. The same seasonal pattern and relative ordering of buildings are reproduced by the disaggregation method (see Figure 16) and are consistent with the validation statistics in (Table 4), where hourly coefficients of determination are 0.91 and weekly coefficients of determination are between 0.89 and 0.95, indicating that the hybrid ICA and PLR approach captures actual heating behavior and benefits from daily and weekly aggregation for reporting and quality assurance. The monthly profiles in Figure 10 confirms a strong concentration of SHL in winter, while the small but non-negligible summer demand at portfolio level is dominated by institutional buildings due to hot water, standby loads, and continuous occupancy and should be tracked as part of routine quality assurance to ensure that warm season suppression remains effective.

Figure 10: Aggregated monthly per-building (submetered) actual SHL and outdoor temperature

Figure 11 presents the monthly share of electricity attributed to space heating for the five submetered buildings K1, O4, O5, I6, and S6, which follows a clear seasonal pattern with heating accounting for approximately 55-73% of total electricity in December and January. On other hand, this reduces to about 10-41% during June to August, indicating that winter electricity use is dominated by heating. I6 maintains the highest shares throughout the year, consistent with DHW and standby loads in a continuously operated building, whereas the day use buildings show a pronounced summer decline. The gradual decrease from April to June and subsequent increase from September to December aligns with outdoor temperature, supporting the method used to derive these shares and suggesting that operational priorities should include review of summer baseloads in S6 and I6 and optimization of winter warm up and evening setback in the day use buildings.

Figure 11: Aggregated monthly per-building (submetered) SHL share in percentage.

3.2.2.1 Temperature sensitivity and outdoor temperature-SHL relationship

Figure 12 shows submetered exemplars for a kindergarten (K1, left) and an office building (O5, right), where hourly SHL is plotted against outdoor temperature and measured values are shown as grey points while estimates from the hybrid ICA and PLR model are shown as green markers. In both buildings, SHL increases monotonically as outdoor temperature decreases and collapses toward zero under mild conditions, indicating an appropriate balance temperature and effective suppression of heating during the warm season. The agreement between measured and estimated loads is close across the full temperature range, particularly for K1, whereas O5 exhibits a steeper temperature sensitivity and a wider scatter that is consistent with higher installed capacity and greater variability in NHL electricity use.

Figure 12: Estimated heating vs. outdoor temperature (scatter) for a) kindergarten (K1), b) Office (O5)

These patterns indicate that the disaggregation method reproduces the physical relationship between temperature and space heating demand required for reliable forecasting. This motivates the subsequent cluster level analysis in which buildings are grouped and their hourly SHL is related to outdoor temperature with simple linear fits used to summarize weather sensitivity.

Figure 13 summarizes the SHL sensitivity of temperature at cluster level by plotting hourly SHL against outdoor temperature for kindergartens, offices, institutions, and schools, with point density indicated by color and a linear regression overlaid in each panel. All clusters exhibit a strong negative regression slope, confirming that SHL increases approximately linearly as outdoor temperature decreases over the main operating range; the absolute slope is largest for institutions (about 3.5 kW per degree Celsius) and offices (about 3.0 kW per degree Celsius), reflecting high installed capacity and long operating hours, while schools show a moderate sensitivity (about 0.94 kW per degree Celsius) and kindergartens the lowest (about 0.28 kW per degree Celsius), consistent with smaller floor areas and shorter, more intermittent schedules.

The intercepts of the regression lines and the spread of points around them indicate NHL baseloads and operational variability, with institutions displaying the broadest scatter due to DHW and process loads, whereas kindergartens and schools are more tightly clustered. Overall, the gradients and density patterns in said figure demonstrate that the disaggregated SHL preserve a physically plausible and group specific response to outdoor temperature that is suitable for subsequent forecasting and flexibility analysis.

Figure 13: Estimated SHL versus outdoor temperature, by building type (scatter with fitted line).

3.2.2.2 Diurnal, weekend, and occupancy effects on heating

The following analysis investigates how disaggregated SHL varies over the day and across the week in order to link heating demand explicitly to occupancy and control schedules. Median and mean hourly profiles for the winter months are used to characterize typical warm up, occupied, and setback periods for each cluster and to distinguish weekday operation from weekend behavior. The resulting diurnal and weekly patterns provide direct evidence of how well existing control strategies align with actual building use, reveal systematic over or under-heating outside core hours, and identify time windows where heating demand is both predictable and adjustable. These insights are essential for quantifying practically available flexibility because they indicate when load reductions are likely to be achievable without compromising comfort and how occupancy constraints differ between schools, kindergartens, institutions, and offices.

Figure 14 shows the median winter weekday SHL by hour of day for schools, kindergartens, institutions, and offices, with separate curves for December to March and interquartile (IQR) bands, and illustrates clear diurnal and occupancy driven patterns: all clusters exhibit a pronounced morning warm up starting around 06:00, a daytime plateau aligned with occupied hours, and an evening setback toward night time baseload, with kindergartens and offices displaying shorter and more concentrated operating windows than schools and institutions.

Figure 14: Estimated SHL using hybrid ICA-PLR method for Dec, Jan, Feb, and Mar in each building type (cluster)

The higher daytime levels and wider variability in January and February compared with December and March reflect both colder conditions and more intensive heating during core occupancy,

confirming that the disaggregated heating profiles capture realistic diurnal control and schedule effects.

Figure 15 presents the weekly mean SHL by hour of week for the same four clusters over December to March and highlights the interaction of diurnal, weekend, and occupancy effects: schools, kindergartens, and offices (day use buildings) show a regular five day pattern with strong daytime peaks from Monday to Friday and markedly reduced loads on Saturdays and Sundays, indicating effective setback during unoccupied periods, while institutions maintain elevated night and weekend loads consistent with extended or continuous occupancy and service requirements. Across all clusters the largest weekday peaks occur in January and February, and the persistence or attenuation of weekend loads by group provides a direct indication of how well heating controls track actual occupancy, which is critical for both flexibility assessment and operational targeting.

Figure 15: Estimated SHL using hybrid ICA-PLR method for Dec, Jan, Feb, and Mar in each building type (cluster)

3.2.2.3 Building Clusters and Heating

Figure 16 summarizes the cluster level temperature response of electricity use by decomposing mean total demand into the mean disaggregated space heating load (SHL) and mean non space heating load (NHL). For each cluster, the curves report the average total load, SHL, and NHL as a function of outdoor temperature, providing a compact signature that separates the temperature driven heating component from the comparatively temperature insensitive baseline demand.

Figure 16: Cluster level temperature response of mean total electricity demand and its disaggregated components: SHL and NHL load.

Across all clusters, the SHL component increases as outdoor temperature decreases, while the NHL component remains comparatively flat. This pattern is consistent with an electrified heating response superimposed on a largely temperature independent base load, and it indicates that the disaggregation recovers the expected thermally driven structure at cluster scale. Kindergartens exhibit the lowest absolute loads and the smallest NHL baseline, with SHL accounting for most of the increase in total demand under cold conditions and approaching low values at mild temperatures. Offices show a larger and more persistent NHL baseline, reflecting continuous plug loads and ventilation related electricity use during occupied periods, while SHL adds a distinct winter uplift that progressively diminishes as temperatures rise. Institutions sustain the highest total demand and the largest NHL baseline, consistent with extended or continuous operation, yet still show substantial SHL sensitivity in cold weather, indicating that heating remains a major driver of winter demand even under around the clock use. Schools fall between kindergartens and offices in absolute magnitude, with a clear heating response at low outdoor temperatures and a moderate NHL baseline at mild temperatures, consistent with larger floor areas and more varied usage patterns than kindergartens.

The relative separation between SHL and NHL curves is directly relevant for flexibility interpretation. Clusters with a large temperature sensitive SHL component and a modest NHL baseline concentrate their controllable winter demand in the heating term, which supports higher technical flexibility potential in cold periods. Clusters with a larger NHL baseline have a smaller fraction of total demand that is temperature driven, which typically reduces the share of demand

that is attributable to space heating and therefore the portion that can be shifted through heating control. The temperature response patterns in Figure 16 are consistent with the submetered heating signals reported for K1, O4, O5, I6, and S6 in Figure 10, supporting that the disaggregation captures the underlying heating signal and its dependence on outdoor conditions at both building and cluster level.

3.2.3 Validation

Validation step uses the five buildings with submetered SHL (K1, S6, O4, O5, I6) as ground truth and defines as portfolio \mathcal{V} , and computes out of sample accuracy at hourly, daily, and weekly resolutions. Table 4 summarizes the portfolio level (portfolio \mathcal{V} consist of submetered datasets) metrics for 2024: for the full year the hybrid ICA-PLR model attains an hourly coefficient of determination of about 0.91 and a Pearson correlation of 0.96 with a nMAE of about 13%, while aggregation to daily averages increases R^2 to about 0.95 and 0.93 for full year and non-summer period (excluding Jun-Aug). When summer months are excluded, the fit improves further, with daily nMAE gets to about 10%, indicating that the method reproduces heating-dominated periods particularly well and that aggregation to reporting intervals used in practice materially tightens residual error for portfolio monitoring.

Table 4: Portfolio-level (portfolio \mathcal{V}) validation metrics (2024)

Metric	N (FY)	N (NS)	ICA-PLR (FY)	ICA-PLR (NS)	PLR (FY)	PLR (NS)	ICA (FY)	ICA (NS)	RFR (FY)	RFR (NS)
R^2 (H)	8784	6576	0.910118	0.874642	0.732733	0.672742	0.062557	0.066922	0.796519	0.757927
Pearson r (H)	8784	6576	0.960591	0.943496	0.932734	0.912039	0.915816	0.905662	0.957129	0.948946
MAE (H) (kWh)	8784	6576	13.781550	16.063205	28.716019	29.853688	59.882464	56.498232	27.35836	28.39581
nMAE (H) (%)	8784	6576	13.744530	13.205537	28.638882	24.542672	59.721607	46.447113	27.28487	23.34415
R^2 (D)	366	274	0.951695	0.931530	0.882632	0.876647	0.062429	0.048161	0.902292	0.896108
Pearson r (D)	366	274	0.982575	0.974145	0.980805	0.972030	0.960353	0.948526	0.992199	0.989591
MAE (D) (kWh)	366	274	255.6928	292.2602	446.1398	407.4246	1398.1731	1304.1977	422.3038	394.4206
nMAE(D) (%)	366	274	10.654280	10.047650	18.589879	14.006900	58.259470	44.837169	17.59667	13.55983

Note: H/D denote hourly/daily aggregation, respectively. FY = full year; NS = non-summer (excluding Jun-Aug, months 6, 7, 8). N is the number of time slices: H = 8,784 (FY) and 6,576 (NS); D = 366 (FY) and 274 (NS).

Figure 17 illustrates the time series behavior for one representative office building (O5) over two weeks in March 2024, overlaying total electricity, the submetered SHL, the proposed ICA-PLR estimate, and the comparison with three benchmark methods (PLR/CPR, RFR, and FastICA). Over this period, the ICA-PLR estimate follows the submetered heating load closely during both baseload hours and morning recovery peaks, whereas the benchmark methods tend to overshoot peak loads, misattribute NHL consumption during daytime and evening hours, and exhibit more erratic responses to short term temperature fluctuations. Figure 18 shows the variation of estimated SHL using the proposed methodology and other techniques for a typical month of the year, when applied to submetered data (actual SHL) of the buildings. As observed, the estimated disaggregated SHL closely follows the actual metered SHL data for the building types. The estimated values are accurate over a wide range of outdoor temperature profile. On the other hand, using techniques

like FastICA, RFR and PLR/CPR, their estimated hourly values deviate to a large extent from actual ones, mainly for highly extensive SHL buildings, institution and office types. The combined evidence from Figures 17-18 and Table 4 shows that the hybrid ICA-PLR approach captures most of the variance in heating demand at hourly resolution and that temporally aggregated outputs provide a robust basis for subsequent flexibility analysis at building and portfolio level.

Figure 17: O5 (office building) March 18–31(2024), total, actual SHL, methods, and outdoor temperature

Figure 18: Estimated SHL using different techniques for the month of March in each building type (submetered)

A. Aggregate performance (all buildings)

Using the building-level SHL estimator from the mask-gated residuals, type-level and portfolio-level aggregates are formed and evaluated with the same metrics. Figure 19 summarizes portfolio-level accuracy over the full year. The proposed method shows the best performance on all panels, with the highest R^2 and Pearson’s r and the lowest MAE and normalized nMAE. RFR ranks second, improving on PLR/CPR but still behind the proposed approach, which indicates added value from the physics-guided mask and HDH anchoring. FastICA performs worst, consistent with warm-season false activation and scale drift. The identical ranking across panels points to a general performance advantage rather than a metric-specific effect.

Figure 19: Performance indices for aggregated accuracy on energy data collected for a year

Figure 20 summarizes portfolio performance after excluding June-August (summer months). The proposed method remains best overall, with higher variance explained and lower errors than PLR/CPR and FastICA. RFR attains a similar (slightly higher) correlation but still has lower R^2 and larger errors, indicating profile shape matching (pattern recognition) but weaker magnitude calibration. The ranking is consistent with the full-year results, showing that performance does not rely on summer near-zero periods and that the mask/HDH steps maintain accuracy through the heating season.

Figure 20: Performance indices for aggregated accuracy on energy data excluding summer months

Table 5 reports portfolio accuracy across time scales (hourly, daily, weekly) for the full year and for the heating season (excluding June–August). The proposed method maintains the highest variance explained and the lowest errors across all slices, with accuracy strengthening under daily and weekly aggregation. Similar rankings in the excluding summer windows indicate that results are driven by heating-season behavior rather than summer near-zero periods.

Table 5: Aggregate performance indices across all buildings

Window	Slice	N	nMAE (%)	R^2	ΔR^2 vs hourly	nMAE reduction vs hourly (pp)
FY	Hourly	8784	13.744530	0.910118	0.000000	0.000000
FY	Daily	366	10.654280	0.951695	0.041577	3.090250
NS	Hourly	6576	13.205537	0.874642	0.000000	0.000000
NS	Daily	274	10.047650	0.931530	0.056888	3.157887

Notes: FY is full year 2024. NS is non-summer (June, July, August excluded). Weekly N is shown using ISO year week grouping (yields 53 weeks).

B. Performance on building types

As discussed in Section 3.2.2.1, SHL varies by building type due to size, vintage, and operation. Figure 21 reports hourly MAE for the four submetered benchmarked buildings (for K1, S6, I6, and O5) by type. The proposed method attains the lowest MAE for S6 (3.31 kW) and K1 (0.67 kW) and achieves its largest MAE reduction relative to best competing model in I6: 12.99 kW versus 21.89 kW for the best competing model (RFR), and substantially lower than PLR/CPR (27.82 kW) and FastICA (37.36 kW). This pattern indicates that the mask gating step and the HDH anchoring applied consistently across buildings are particularly beneficial when heating is strongly temperature driven and the aggregate load is strongly affected by NHL variability. Residual error at I6 is higher and is plausibly explained by site specifics: a medical rehabilitation center in a 1950 building with direct electric panel heaters (on/off control, limited thermal storage), a higher comfort setpoint (~22 °C), and greater envelope losses (possibly), all of which increase variability and reduce separability from the NHL baseline. In O5, a planned shutdown/renovation during

October–December elevated errors for all models. Overall, the type-level results align with the portfolio findings: the hybrid approach is most advantageous in institutions and kindergartens, performs best or close to best in schools and offices, and remains robust across differing heating systems and operating conditions.

Figure 21: Performance indices on energy data for a year from each building type

When control schedules are regular, the cold-hour mask with day/night lags aligns estimated heating activation with actual operation. When plant dynamics drive short-term fluctuations, daily/weekly aggregation reduces high-frequency variability and improves agreement.

C. Per-building quantitative comparison

Figure 22 illustrates the monthly SHL budgets with pronounced winter peaks and shoulder-season tapering; institutions (I1–I6) account for the largest winter totals, whereas all clusters approach zero in summer, consistent with correct mask gating and monthly energy conservation. The institutional dominance is expected given continuous occupancy, older envelopes, and the prevalence of direct-electric heating in this group.

Figure 22: Monthly average per cluster SHL by each building cluster

Figure 23 illustrates that, across the four submetered sites, the proposed ICA-PLR closely follows the metered space-heating load (SHL) during winter ramp-up and shoulder-season decay while remaining near zero in summer. This indicates strong seasonal specificity and effective mask gating (low warm-season leakage) and good temperature anchoring. The benchmark methods exhibit characteristic failure modes: PLR/CPR tends to dampen cold-spell peaks and over-assign heating under mild conditions; FastICA shows substantial warm-season leakage, in some cases

approaching the total load; and RFR captures the overall shape but retains magnitude bias, especially during rapid ramps. Site effects explain the remaining discrepancies.

In the said figure, type-specific behavior explains the residual differences. K1 (kindergarten) and S6 (school) show clean summer suppression and close winter tracking, whereas I6 (institution) has high and persistent heating demand, reducing separability from the non-heating baseline and leading to some under-capture of January-March peaks. O4 (office) shows higher NHL variability; RFR is competitive in correlation but less accurate in level. Overall, the hybrid approach reduces spurious heating allocation via a physics-informed temperature/season mask and stabilizes the component scaling using an HDH-based calibration, yielding lower seasonal leakage and more accurate peak amplitudes over the full year.

Figure 23: SHL estimation comparison of different methods for selected building types

After validation on submetered sites, the proposed method is applied to assets without SHL meters and aggregated by type and presented in Figure 24 in four clusters. In the said figure, the type curves show a clear seasonal pattern: SHL remains close to zero from June to September, when outdoor temperature is generally above about 10 °C, and rises through autumn with peaks in January to March. Peaks coincide with increases in total electricity and with low temperature, which indicates correct attribution of the heating share. Summer suppression confirms that the cold-hour mask prevents activation in warm periods, and the degree-hour calibration preserves winter amplitude at aggregate scale.

As observed, differences across the building types are consistent with earlier results. The building types; institution display the largest and most persistent SHL, reflecting continuous occupancy, older envelopes, and direct electric heating. On the other hand, office buildings show moderate

winter SHL on top of a higher non-heating baseline and schools and kindergartens exhibit the smallest magnitudes and the sharpest shoulder-season taper. The coherence of these aggregates with the site-level comparisons and with the portfolio metrics supports transfer of type-level parameters to buildings with no sub-metering and indicates reliable extraction of the heating component from whole-building electricity aggregate at hourly resolution.

Figure 24: Variation of total estimated SHL for each building types

D. Effect of temporal aggregation

Temporal aggregation improves accuracy by averaging out high frequency control driven variability and short timing mismatches between estimated and metered heating, while preserving the underlying seasonal energy signal. This effect is quantified in Tables 4 and 5. For the sub metered validation portfolio V , moving from hourly to daily aggregation increases R^2 from 0.910 to 0.952 in the full year and from 0.875 to 0.932 in the non-summer window, while nMAE decreases from about 13.7 percent to 10.7 percent in the full year and from about 13.2 percent to 10.0 percent in the non-summer window (Table 4). The same trend holds for the full building portfolio, where R^2 increases from 0.822 at hourly resolution to 0.873 at daily and 0.890 at weekly resolution in the full year and nMAE decreases from 22.27 percent to 19.76 percent daily and 18.63 percent weekly (Table 5). In the non-summer window, R^2 increases from 0.793 hourly to 0.932 daily and 0.947 weekly, while nMAE decreases from 17.96 percent to 15.28 percent daily and 14.03 percent weekly (Table 5). These consistent improvements support reporting at multiple time scales, with daily aggregation suitable for operational monitoring and weekly aggregation suitable for planning level summaries.

3.2.4 Uncertainty and recommended reporting

For portfolio-level communication, this study recommends expressing SHL estimates with uncertainty bands of approximately ± 20 – 25% at hourly resolution and ± 10 – 20% for weekly winter aggregates. At building level, these intervals can be narrowed where space heating is the dominant share of electricity use and metering is stable and widened where NHL variability or data issues are significant. Weekly winter aggregation should be adopted as the primary reporting resolution for management and measurement and verification because it balances temporal detail with robustness to random error and model misspecification, while daily views are most useful for diagnosing specific events such as cold spells or control failures. The time aggregation effects and validation slices (see Table 5), where R^2 increases and nMAE decreases from hourly to daily and weekly scales, support these recommended uncertainty ranges and reporting practices.

3.2.5 SHL disaggregation summary

Electricity consumption for space heating accounts for 2.91 GWh, or 42% of total electricity use across the 22 buildings in 2024. When summer months (June–August) are excluded, the portfolio share of space heating rises to 45.21%, and during December, January, and February space heating represents on average about 54% of total electricity use. At building level, I6, S6, and O4 each reach winter averages of roughly 55% space-heating share, with daily and weekly site-level maxima approaching 73%. Institutions and the largest schools dominate both the proportional contribution of heating (the share of each building’s electricity used for space heating) and the absolute contribution (total SHL in kilowatt-hours), whereas offices show lower fractions due to higher NHL variability and reduced occupancy during weekends and holidays. Submetered parameters confirm expected thermodynamic behavior, including plausible balance temperatures, temperature sensitivities, and response lags, and the accuracy of the hybrid ICA-PLR method improves further when results are aggregated to weekly winter-time scales.

Overall, space heating is the single largest driver of winter electricity consumption in this portfolio and therefore represents a primary target for reducing losses, improving efficiency, and quantifying flexibility for EFaaS. Day-use buildings (schools, kindergartens, offices) concentrate heating demand in morning warm-up periods and early evenings, which makes these windows particularly suitable for setpoint optimization, preheating adjustments, and refinement of schedule alignment. Institutions operate more continuously, so their short-term flexibility is smaller, but persistent gains can be achieved by tightening night setbacks, optimizing heat distribution, and managing DHW and standby loads.

3.3 Flexibility characterization and quantification

This subsection describes how space-heating flexibility is quantified from the hourly SHL time series derived in Section 3.2 and from weather and calendar data. The aim is to compute *operationally meaningful* indicators of how much electric space-heating demand can be

temporarily reduced, shifted, or advanced without compromising comfort, in line with the IEA EBC Annex 67/82 terminology for building energy flexibility [37], [38], [39].

Following Annex 67/82, flexibility is characterized by: (i) *capacity* (kW) – the power that can be curtailed or increased, (ii) *duration* (h) – how long this capacity can be sustained, (iii) *shiftable energy* (kWh) – the energy moved in time, and (iv) *rebound* (kWh, %) during the recovery period after an event [38], [39]. The method developed here is based on *uncertainty-aware* flexibility envelopes and capacity–duration curves for each building and their cluster and finally aggregating them to portfolio-level availability metrics.

The core flexibility metrics are:

- Shiftable energy, defined as the energy reduction within a specified flexibility event window relative to a baseline.
- Peak-shaving capacity, defined as the constant power reduction that can be sustained over a given duration.
- Event duration, defined as the length of the flexibility event in hours.
- Rebound energy and rebound peak, defined over a recovery window following the event.
- Availability metrics that describe how often a given building or portfolio can supply at least a given capacity for a given duration under specified outdoor conditions.

These metrics are derived using a sequence of modelling steps described in the following subsections.

The framework has six main components: (i) definition of event-level flexibility metrics (shiftable energy, peak-shaving capacity, rebound, portfolio flexibility factor); (ii) Construction of a baseline ensemble with prediction intervals; (iii) a non-intrusive occupancy proxy based on NHL; (iv) identification of thermal storability via simple ARX models and effective time constants; (v) Derivation of safety envelopes and empirical ramp limits; (vi) a chance-constrained, energy-neutral optimization that yields building-level capacity–duration points and portfolio aggregation.

Unless otherwise stated, the analysis is restricted to heating-season hours using the SHL estimates produced by the hybrid ICA-PLR method in Section 3.2.

3.3.1 Event definition and core metrics

Figure 25 provides a schematic overview of the baseline heating trajectory, the optimized flexible trajectory, and the event and recovery windows defined in this subsection.

Let $\hat{h}_{i,t}$ denote the estimated (disaggregated) space-heating load for building index i at hour index t , obtained from the hybrid ICA-PLR method in Section 3.2 (kW). This estimated SHL series $\hat{h}_{i,t}$ is used as the input to (i) fit the counterfactual baseline heating trajectory and (ii) derive empirical feasibility constraints (safety envelopes, ramp-rate limits, and recovery-horizon lengths) in Sections 3.3.2-3.3.5. A hypothetical flexibility activation is represented by a flexible (activated)

heating trajectory $h_{i,t}^{\text{flex}}$ (kW), defined over a local optimization window $W(t_0)$ such that $W(t_0) = H_e \cup H_r$. Here, t_0 is the event start hour (hour index), d is the event duration (h), $H_e = \{t_0, \dots, t_0 + d - 1\}$ is the event horizon (the set of hours during which flexibility is delivered), and H_r is the recovery horizon (the set of hours following the event used to capture rebound). Thus, the optimization window $W(t_0)$ shifts with the event start hour t_0 because the event horizon H_e and recovery horizon H_r are anchored to t_0 . For the Verdal analysis, the event duration $d \in \{1,2,3,4\}$ h, and the recovery horizon length (i.e., the number of hours in H_r) is chosen as a multiple of the identified thermal time constant τ_i (Section 3.3.4) to avoid unrealistically short rebound dynamics [39], [40].

Figure 25: Schematic illustration of a demand-response event. The orange curve shows the counterfactual baseline heating trajectory $\tilde{h}_{i,t}^{\text{base}}$; the blue dashed curve shows a feasible flexible trajectory $h_{i,t}^{\text{flex}}$. The event window H_e (left shaded region) and recovery window H_r (right shaded region) define the optimization horizon. The orange shaded area represents event energy E_{event} , the blue shaded area represents rebound energy E_{rec} , and the constant vertical gap C in H_e corresponds to the conservative capacity $\gamma(i, t_0, d)$.

A counterfactual baseline heating trajectory $\tilde{h}_{i,t}^{\text{base}}$ (kW) represents the heating that would have occurred in the absence of activation and is produced by the baseline ensemble in Section 3.3.2; the event energy $E_{\text{event}}(i, t_0, d)$ (kWh), rebound energy $E_{\text{rec}}(i, t_0, d)$ (kWh), net shiftable energy $E_{\text{net}}(i, t_0, d)$ (kWh), and conservative peak-shaving capacity $\gamma(i, t_0, d)$ (kW) are then defined relative to $\tilde{h}_{i,t}^{\text{base}}$ and $h_{i,t}^{\text{flex}}$ over the event horizon H_e and recovery horizon H_r .

$$E_{\text{event}}(i, t_0, d) = \sum_{t \in H_e} \max(\tilde{h}_{i,t}^{\text{base}} - h_{i,t}^{\text{flex}}, 0) \Delta t \quad (10)$$

Equation (10) defines the event energy reduction as the baseline-to-flexible reduction accumulated over the event horizon. The positive-part operator enforces the convention that only downward deviations (curtailment relative to baseline) contribute to E_{event} ; if the flexible trajectory exceeds the baseline at any event hour, that hour contributes zero rather than a negative offset. This definition therefore measures delivered curtailment energy, independent of any later compensation. The rebound (recovery) energy $E_{\text{rec}}(i, t_0, d)$ (kWh) is defined as the total excess heating energy above the baseline accumulated during the recovery horizon H_r :

$$E_{\text{rec}}(i, t_0, d) = \sum_{t \in H_r} \max(h_{i,t}^{\text{flex}} - \tilde{h}_{i,t}^{\text{base}}, 0) \Delta t, \quad (11)$$

Equation (11) defines the rebound (recovery) energy as the amount by which the flexible trajectory exceeds the baseline during the recovery horizon. Here the positive-part operator ensures that only upward deviations are counted as rebound, so recovery that merely returns to baseline does not create artificial cancellation. Together, Eqs. (10) and (11) separate “delivered reduction” from “payback” in a way that matches Annex-style reporting practice. The net shiftable energy is

$$E_{\text{net}}(i, t_0, d) = E_{\text{event}}(i, t_0, d) - E_{\text{rec}}(i, t_0, d). \quad (12)$$

Equation (12) defines the net shiftable energy as curtailed event energy minus rebound energy, yielding the net amount of energy effectively moved (or not fully compensated) within the event-plus-recovery accounting window. Reporting E_{event} and E_{rec} alongside E_{net} avoids ambiguity about whether a large curtailment was achieved at the cost of an equally large rebound. These definitions follow Annex-style net-energy accounting, which requires that rebound be reported explicitly alongside event energy [37], [38].

For constant-capacity events, a central metric is the conservative peak-shaving capacity γ (kW), defined as the minimum sustained reduction over the event horizon:

$$\gamma(i, t_0, d) = \min_{t \in H_e} (\tilde{h}_{i,t}^{\text{base}} - h_{i,t}^{\text{flex}}). \quad (13)$$

Equation (13) defines the conservative peak-shaving capacity as a worst-hour (minimum) reduction over the event horizon. The minimum operator makes γ a “firm/conservative” constant reduction level: if reductions fluctuate across hours in the event, γ is set by the weakest hour rather than the average. This is the appropriate notion of capacity when an operator requires a sustained, non-varying reduction over the full event duration. The optimization in Section 3.3.6 chooses $h_{i,t}^{\text{flex}}$ to maximize γ subject to safety and comfort constraints. For pure load-shifting analysis, an energy-neutrality condition is imposed:

$$\sum_{t \in W(t_0)} (\tilde{h}_{i,t}^{\text{base}} - h_{i,t}^{\text{flex}}) \Delta t = 0, \quad (14)$$

Equation (14) enforces energy neutrality over the optimization window, meaning that the flexible trajectory is constrained to redistribute energy in time rather than change total energy across the event-plus-recovery window. Under this constraint, reductions during the event must be balanced

by increases during recovery, so the resulting flexibility characterization corresponds to pure load shifting rather than net energy savings and that the net energy impact over event plus recovery is zero and only temporal redistribution is evaluated [37], [39].

At portfolio level, a simple technical flexibility factor is defined as the fraction of baseline heating energy during the event that can be reliably shifted:

$$\text{PF}(t_0, d) = \frac{\sum_{i=1}^B E_{\text{event}}(i, t_0, d)}{\sum_{i=1}^B \sum_{t \in H_e} \tilde{h}_{i,t}^{\text{base}} \Delta t}, \quad (15)$$

where, $B = 22$ is the number of buildings. This indicator is analogous to market-independent flexibility ratios proposed in [38], [41], [40] but applied here specifically to space-heating demand. Equation (15) defines a portfolio-level flexibility factor as the fraction of baseline heating energy during the event horizon that is curtailed when aggregating across all B buildings. The numerator aggregates delivered event energy reductions, while the denominator normalizes by the portfolio's baseline heating energy during the same event hours, making $\text{PF}(t_0, d)$ dimensionless and comparable across different event timings and durations.

3.3.2 Baseline ensemble and prediction uncertainty

Credible flexibility estimates require a fair and uncertainty-aware baseline model, i.e., a counterfactual that reproduces the dependence of SHL on outdoor temperature, time of week, and occupancy, and that provides prediction intervals for event hours [42], [43], [44]. Classical change-point linear regression (CPLR) relates heating to heating-degree hours below a base temperature, with a flat segment above the breakpoint, and is well established in building energy analysis and demand response baseline practice [42]. CPQR generalizes this to conditional quantiles and provides natural prediction bands that capture heteroscedasticity and regime changes [44].

In this framework, a baseline ensemble is constructed from three components:

- a CPLR model that relates SHL to heating-degree hours using a variable-base degree-day change-point regression with calendar terms;
- a CPQR model that estimates conditional quantiles (e.g. 20th, 50th, 80th percentile) of SHL as a function of temperature and time-of-week features, used to represent state-dependent uncertainty [44].
- a parsimonious time-of-week-temperature-solar (TOWST) model that includes hour-of-week indicators, outdoor temperature, heating-degree terms, and simple solar proxies to reduce diurnal and solar aliasing in winter [45].

The models are trained on the SHL estimates from Section 3.2, stratified by temperature band and season. Out-of-fold prediction errors are used to form a stacked ensemble, with weights inversely proportional to squared error, so that better performing components receive larger weight. For each

building and hour, the ensemble baseline $\hat{h}_{i,t}^{\text{ens}}$ is then adjusted locally using a day-of (pre-event) affine correction, fitted on the few hours directly preceding a candidate event. This reduces local bias without overfitting, in line with best practice for demand-response baselines [43].

Prediction uncertainty is quantified via a residual bootstrap: baseline residuals are resampled within strata defined by hour-of-week, outdoor-temperature band, and occupancy state, and propagated through the ensemble to obtain empirical prediction intervals $[\tilde{h}_{i,t}^L, \tilde{h}_{i,t}^U]$ at each hour and building. These intervals later inform conservative comfort bounds and chance-constraint surrogates in the optimization (Section 3.3.6).

3.3.3 Occupancy proxy and stratification

Occupancy is a major determinant of heating flexibility because comfort constraints are tighter during occupied periods and more relaxed during nights and weekends [39], [46]. Direct occupancy sensing is not available for the Verval buildings, so a non-intrusive occupancy proxy is derived from NHL, short-horizon variability, and calendar information.

For each building, NHL is obtained as the difference between total electric power and estimated SHL from Section 3.2. A compact feature vector is constructed that includes:

- NHL level and short-term ramps (e.g. 1–2 h differences);
- intra-hour variance (as a proxy for appliance switching);
- hour-of-week and month dummies;
- weekend and holiday flags.

A logistic classification model maps these features into an occupancy presence score $s_t \in [0,1]$, which is then monotonically calibrated on a subset of hours with high-confidence occupancy labels (e.g. regular school hours, nights in institutions). Thresholds are applied to categorize each hour as “Occupied”, “Unoccupied”, or “Uncertain”. Compared with purely schedule-based occupancy models, this non-intrusive proxy captures deviations due to extended opening, evening use, or atypical closures [46], [47].

In subsequent steps, occupancy classes are used to:

- condition baseline residual bootstrapping and prediction intervals;
- construct occupancy-conditioned safety envelopes (Section 3.3.5);
- tighten lower bounds during occupied hours (smaller allowed reduction) and widen them during uncertain hours to account for misclassification risk.

3.3.4 Storability and feasible event durations

The thermal storability of each building limits how long heating can be curtailed without violating comfort, and influences the magnitude and shape of rebound [39], [40]. To characterize storability

from data, this study uses autoregressive models with exogenous inputs (ARX) fitted to residual heating demand after baseline correction.

For each building, the residual series

$$y_{i,t} = h_{i,t} - \tilde{h}_{i,t}^{\text{base}} \quad (16)$$

is modelled as an ARX process with outdoor temperature and, where relevant, derived occupancy class indicators from the non-intrusive occupancy proxy as exogenous inputs. The dominant eigenvalue of the fitted AR part is converted into an effective e-folding time constant $\tau_i(h)$, which provides a simple summary of how quickly thermal deviations decay. A separate, coarse 1R1C (first-order resistance–capacitance) grey-box model is used as a plausibility check on τ_i to ensure that the inferred dynamics remain within physically reasonable ranges for the envelope and plant type [39], [40].

The identified time constants serve two roles:

- they inform the recovery horizon length in the optimization (e.g. at least one to two e-folding times, longer under very cold conditions);
- they support temperature-banded stress tests, where events in the coldest bands use more conservative assumptions about storability and thus shorter feasible durations.

3.3.5 Safety envelopes and empirical ramp limits

To avoid unrealistic or unsafe flexibility trajectories, this study constrains SHL to remain within empirical safety envelopes derived from historical operation. For each building, and for each combination of hour-of-week, outdoor-temperature band, and occupancy class, the empirical distribution of observed SHL is summarized by lower and upper quantiles. The lower envelope $L_{i,t}$ represents typical minimum heating levels historically associated with acceptable comfort under the given conditions, while the upper envelope $U_{i,t}$ reflects typical maxima and prevents unrealistic overshoots during pre-heating or rebound.

During occupied hours, the lower envelope is tightened by using a higher quantile and by incorporating the upper end of the baseline prediction interval, leading to more conservative comfort bounds. During uncertain occupancy hours, lower bounds are widened by an additive margin to account for misclassification risk. In the coldest temperature bands (e.g. below approximately -15 °C), both lower and upper envelopes are tightened using more conservative quantiles and the lower end of the storability confidence interval, reflecting reduced flexibility of heat pump systems and higher comfort risk [39], [40].

In addition to envelopes, empirical ramp limits are derived to bound the rate of change of SHL. For each stratum (hour-of-week \times temperature band \times occupancy), the distribution of observed hourly changes $\Delta h_{i,t} = h_{i,t} - h_{i,t-1}$ is summarized, and high-percentile values (e.g. 90th percentile) are used as maximum allowed upward and downward ramps. These non-parametric

ramp limits prevent the optimization from proposing abrupt curtailment or recovery profiles that would be technically or operationally unrealistic.

Together, safety envelopes and ramp limits provide a measurement-based characterization of feasible operating regions for SHL under different conditions, analogous to the flexibility trajectories and “safe envelopes” used in previous Annex-aligned studies [39], [40], [46]. Figure 26 shows each of the demand response safety envelopes, capacity and rebound and the overall optimization window details.

Figure 26: Schematic illustration of a demand-response event showing safety envelopes, occupancy, day of adjustment, and baseline ensemble.

3.3.6 Optimization and capacity-duration curves

For each building, with event start hour and event duration, a linear optimization problem is solved over the local window $W(t_0)$. The decision variables are the flexible trajectory $h_{i,t}^{flex}$ and the constant shed level γ . The objective is to maximize γ subject to:

- safety envelopes: $L_{i,t} \leq h_{i,t}^{flex} \leq U_{i,t}$ for all $t \in W(t_0)$;
- comfort-related bounds during occupied hours, using conservative quantiles of the baseline and bootstrap-derived prediction intervals.
- ramp limits on hour-to-hour changes, based on empirical ramps.
- energy-neutrality, if pure shifting is considered (Eq. (14));
- the constant-capacity condition over the event horizon (Eq. (13)).

Baseline prediction intervals, occupancy classifications, and storability estimates enter these constraints indirectly through the construction of envelopes, ramps, and recovery horizons

(Sections 3.3.2–3.3.5). Instead of explicit probabilistic constraints, the optimization uses deterministic surrogates based on high-confidence quantiles (e.g. 90–95%) so that the resulting capacities can be interpreted as “conservative” under typical winter conditions.

For each building and event duration d , the optimization is run across a set of candidate winter start hours t_0 (stratified by temperature band). The resulting set of capacities $\gamma(i, t_0, d)$ is summarized by representative quantiles (e.g. median and 10th percentile). Plotting these against duration yields building-level capacity–duration curves, which are Annex-aligned representations of the trade-off between achievable shedding depth and event length [37], [38], [41].

3.3.7 Aggregation and availability indicators

To assess portfolio performance, building-level capacities are aggregated by cluster and for the full set of 22 buildings. For each duration d , a weighted fleet-level capacity is computed from the individual $\gamma_i(d)$, with weights based on floor area and data coverage so that buildings with incomplete time series do not dominate the aggregate [38], [41], [46].

In addition, availability indicators are constructed that describe how often a given building or cluster can supply at least a certain capacity for a given duration. For a threshold space-heating down capacity x (kW) and duration d (h), the availability of building-level down-capacity is defined as the fraction of winter events for which $\gamma(i, t_0, d) \geq x$. By aggregating across buildings and conditioning on outdoor-temperature bands, availability surfaces are obtained, meaning two-dimensional maps of availability over capacity x and duration d , reported separately for each outdoor-temperature band, which show how flexibility varies with capacity, duration, and climate regime.

These availability indicators provide a direct bridge between individual flexibility envelopes and EFaaS scenario design, allowing operators to infer, for example, how many school-type buildings are required to reliably provide a certain portfolio-level down-capacity in a given temperature band [38], [41], [46].

3.3.8 Supplementary economic flexibility indicators

This subsection summarizes additional flexibility indicators from the literature that quantify the economic value of load shifting under time varying electricity prices. The computation is illustrated using a published Latvian case study. These indicators are included as general reference metrics and are primarily applied in the HPSS case study in Section 3.4.2. The following parameters are used for evaluation of flexibility:

- Reduction of demand during peak hours [14]; (in terms of change in the energy demand)
- Load shifting index [48]; (a difference in an equivalent power demand (net energy demand divided by the duration time for either peak or off-peak hours) during peak and off-peak hours relative to the total equivalent power demand)
- Total amount of energy shifted or energy processed (stored in and discharged from) by an energy storage [49] and [50]:

- Economic effectiveness of a shifted demand profile (named “flexibility factor”), which is calculated as a difference between shifted demand during low energy prices and shifted demand during high prices relative to total shifted demand [50].

The flexibility factor according to [50]:

$$FF = \left(\int_0^{t_{\text{low price}}} P_{\text{NEW}} dt - \int_0^{t_{\text{high price}}} P_{\text{NEW}} dt \right) / \left(\int_0^{t_{\text{low price}}} P_{\text{NEW}} dt + \int_0^{t_{\text{high price}}} P_{\text{NEW}} dt \right)$$

The one parameter found in literature that addresses also economic side of energy flexibility “flexibility factor” FF does not capture its improvement, and it ignores energy demand when energy prices are within some boundaries $\pm\sigma$ around an average price. Thus, a new and more universal parameter Energy cost flexibility improvement factor (ECFIF) has been devised:

$$ECFIF = \frac{\int_0^{t_{\text{CO}}} (\Delta T_E^t |P_{\text{NEW}}^t - P_{\text{REF}}^t|) dt}{\int_0^{t_{\text{CO}}} |\Delta T_E P_{\text{REF}}| dt}, \tag{17}$$

$$\Delta T_E^t = \begin{cases} T_{\text{E AVG}} - T_E^t, & \text{if } P^t \geq 0, \\ T_{\text{E SELL}}^t - T_{\text{E AVG}}, & \text{if } P^t < 0, \end{cases} \tag{18}$$

where, $ECFIF$ — an energy cost flexibility improvement factor, p.u.;

t_{CO} — length of a control (analysis) period, h;

ΔT_E^t — a difference between an average energy price (tariff) during t_{CO} and an energy tariff during a time interval t , EUR;

$P_{\text{NEW}}^t, P_{\text{REF}}^t$ — shifted and an expected existing power demand (supply represented as negative values) during a time interval t , kW;

$T_{\text{E AVG}}$ — an average energy price (tariff) during t_{CO} , EUR;

$T_E^t, T_{\text{E SELL}}^t$ — an energy price (tariff) for buying and selling during a time interval t , EUR;

P^t — a power demand (P_{NEW}^t or P_{REF}^t) during a time interval t , kW.

The correctness of changes in this factor has been elaborated upon in cases of change in demand and supply profiles as well as in cases where there is a change from energy demand to supply and vice versa.

Figure 27: Illustration of determination of the ECFIF for a shifted daily demand profile from study [49] (Multi-story building in Latvia study) with green areas representing economically beneficial demand shifting (buying more electricity, when electricity is relatively cheap, or buying less, when it is expensive) and red areas representing economically detrimental demand shifting (buying less electricity, when electricity is relatively cheap, or buying more, when it is expensive).

Given that *ECFIF* is already expressed in p.u. (per unit), obtaining of a coefficient capturing the impact of support to improvements in flexibility is simple:

$$CO_{\text{FLEX}} = \frac{ECFIF}{SUP}, \quad (19)$$

where, CO_{FLEX} — a coefficient of a relative impact of monetary support to improvements in flexibility of energy supply systems of buildings, p.u./EUR/m²;

SUP is the relative total monetary support provided for the analysed improvements, EUR/m².

These indicators are primarily used in the HPSS case study in Section 3.4.2 to evaluate equipment portfolios and control strategies. For the Verdal public-building analysis in Sections 3.3.1–3.3.7 and 3.3.9, the focus is on Annex-style metrics (capacity, duration, shiftable energy, rebound, availability), but the same event-level results can be combined with price profiles and storage operation to derive the above indicators where required.

3.3.9 Flexibility quantification and characterization results (Verdal)

This subsection applies the flexibility framework from Section 3.3 to the 22-building Verdal portfolio. Results are first summarized at cluster level to highlight how much *technical* space-heating flexibility is available in winter and how it is distributed across building types. The subsection then zooms in to building-level rankings, the mix of flexibility “modes” (pre-heating, balanced shifting, rebound-dominated), and seasonal patterns of flexible heating energy.

To quantify flexible energy at portfolio and cluster level, each winter candidate event window is evaluated with the optimization described in Section 3.3.6. For every building and event, the model computes the downward event energy E_{event} (kWh) and its associated rebound. The quantity

$$E_{\text{shift,total}} = \sum_{\text{all events}} E_{\text{event}} \quad (20)$$

is used here as a *cumulative flexible heating-energy indicator* for each building and cluster.

Two points are important for interpretation:

- $E_{\text{shift,total}}$ is a diagnostic indicator, not a single physically realizable energy budget. It sums many overlapping candidate events and therefore cannot be interpreted as “this fraction of annual heating energy is freely shiftable at any time”.
- Instead, $E_{\text{shift,total}}$ expresses how much *event-level* heating energy could, in principle, be temporarily reduced and later recovered under the imposed safety constraints, if each candidate window were activated once.

At portfolio level, the sum of $E_{\text{shift,total}}$ across all buildings is about 131 MWh of SHL. For comparison, annual SHL in 2024 is about 2.91 GWh (Section 3.2), so if all candidate events were called once, the total heating energy temporarily reduced across these events would correspond to roughly 4.5 % of annual space-heating electricity. This 4.5 % should be read as a cumulative

volume over many potential events, not as a static fraction of “flexible load” available at every hour. The distribution of this cumulative indicator by cluster is:

- Schools (S1–S6): about 62.5 MWh ($\approx 48\%$ of portfolio $E_{\text{shift,total}}$).
- Institutions (I1–I6): about 40.3 MWh ($\approx 31\%$).
- Offices (O1–O5): about 22.9 MWh ($\approx 18\%$).
- Kindergartens (K1–K5): about 5.4 MWh ($\approx 4\%$).

This ranking reflects both the installed electric heating capacities and the strength of night/weekend setback routines in schools and in 24/7 institutions. Beyond energy volumes, the model also delivers, for each building, event and hour, a conservative constant downward capacity C_{down} (kW) and an upward headroom C_{up} (kW). The cluster-level averages of these capacities are summarized in Table 6.

Table 6: Cluster-level cumulative flexible-heating indicator and average capacities

Cluster	Number of buildings	Sum of $E_{\text{shift,total}}$ [kWh]	Share of portfolio flexible energy [%]	Mean $C_{\text{down,mean}}$ [kW]	Mean $C_{\text{up,mean}}$ [kW]	Mean business-hours upward headroom $C_{\text{up,BH}}$ [kW]
Schools	6	62 518.0	47.7	1.59	1.69	1.72
Kindergartens	5	5 407.6	4.1	0.19	0.19	0.21
Offices	5	22 881.3	17.5	0.78	0.79	0.85
Institutions	6	40 303.3	30.7	1.10	1.14	1.40

Notes:

- “Share of portfolio cumulative flexible energy” is the share of portfolio $E_{\text{shift,total}}$, not the share of annual heating energy.
- $C_{\text{down,mean}}$ and $C_{\text{up,mean}}$ are averages of the conservative constant capacities over all evaluated winter events for the buildings in each cluster.
- $C_{\text{up,BH}}$ is the average upward headroom during business hours only (occupied daytime hours).

These values show that, in absolute terms, schools and institutions are the main providers of technical space-heating flexibility at portfolio level, while kindergartens contribute small volumes.

3.3.9.1 Building-level rankings and availability

To understand which specific buildings contribute most to the portfolio, three building-level indicators are used. First, the cumulative flexible energy $E_{\text{shift,total}}$ [kWh] is defined as the sum of event-level downward energy over all candidate winter events for that building, computed as in Section 3.3.1. Second, the mean conservative downward capacity $C_{\text{down,mean}}$ [kW] is the average firm shedding capacity across all winter event hours and durations, after applying safety envelopes, ramp limits, and energy-neutrality. Third, the mean upward headroom indicators $C_{\text{up,mean}}$ and $C_{\text{up,BH}}$ [kW] describe the average upward capacity over all winter hours and over business hours (weekdays 08:00–18:00), respectively. All of these metrics are aggregated over many candidate

hours and events; they are intended to rank and compare buildings, not to imply that a fixed fraction of instantaneous heating demand is always flexible.

Figure 28 complements these scalar indicators by visualizing their underlying temporal structure for the representative school S6. The top panel shows the seasonal variation of mean downward and upward capacity headroom by month, alongside the building’s total $E_{\text{shift},\text{total}}$, while the bottom panel shows how mean capacity depends on the event start hour, highlighting the typical morning warm-up window where flexibility is highest.

Figure 28: S6 (School) flexibility fingerprint used to contextualize building-level ranking indicators. The top panel shows mean conservative downward capacity C_d and upward headroom C_u by month (weighted across evaluated candidate events and durations), and cumulative shiftable energy $E_{\text{shift},\text{total}}$. The bottom panel shows the corresponding diurnal mean C_d and C_u by event start hour (0–23), with business hours (08:00–18:00) shaded.

Within the school cluster, two buildings clearly dominate the flexibility potential. S1 has a mean downward capacity $C_{\text{down},\text{mean}}$ of about 3.5 kW and a mean upward capacity $C_{\text{up},\text{mean}}$ of about 4.1 kW, with a cumulative shiftable energy $E_{\text{shift},\text{total}}$ of approximately 26.8 MWh and a business-hours upward headroom $C_{\text{up},\text{BH}}$ around 3.5 kW. S4 is the second-largest contributor, with $C_{\text{down},\text{mean}}$ of roughly 2.1 kW, $C_{\text{up},\text{mean}}$ of about 2.2 kW, $E_{\text{shift},\text{total}}$ of about 12.5 MWh, and $C_{\text{up},\text{BH}}$ close to 2.6 kW. S1 is a large multi-use facility (school plus recreational centers including swimming pools and sports areas) with extensive evening and weekend use. Although the main space heating is

supplied by a bio-pellet system, several zones rely on direct electric heating, which is the part captured in the SHL and therefore in the flexibility metrics. High heating intensity combined with long operating hours explains both the high cumulative flexible energy and the relatively large firm capacities. S2 and S3 form a second tier, with $C_{\text{down,mean}}$ between roughly 1.2 and 1.8 kW and $E_{\text{shift,total}}$ between about 7.2 and 11.0 MWh. The smaller schools S5 and S6, and the newer, well-insulated S6, provide lower but still relevant capacities, with mean downward capacities in the range 0.4–0.6 kW and cumulative shiftable energy between approximately 1.8 and 3.1 MWh. These smaller buildings contribute less in absolute terms but nonetheless add meaningful volumes when aggregated across the portfolio.

In the institutions cluster, the 24/7 building I6 is the single largest contributor. Its cumulative flexible energy $E_{\text{shift,total}}$ is around 13.7 MWh, with symmetric mean capacities $C_{\text{down,mean}}$ and $C_{\text{up,mean}}$ of approximately 2.3 and 2.4 kW and a business-hours upward headroom $C_{\text{up,BH}}$ on the order of 2.8 kW. Other institutional buildings (I5, I4, I1, and I2) each offer between about 4.1 and 9.4 MWh of flexible energy, with mean downward capacities ranging roughly from 0.7 to 1.5 kW and mean upward capacities of similar magnitude. These buildings do not exhibit the deep night and weekend setbacks seen in schools, but they operate continuously and maintain a relatively high baseline. Their flexibility primarily arises from tightening these baselines and exploiting moderate temperature slack, instead of from complete shutdowns.

Offices show more modest absolute capacities, reflecting smaller floor areas and lower SHL intensity compared with schools and institutions. O3 and O5 sit at the upper end of the office distribution, with mean downward capacities just above 1 kW, mean upward capacities around 1.0–1.1 kW, and cumulative shiftable energy $E_{\text{shift,total}}$ of approximately 6.3 and 6.1 MWh, respectively. O2 delivers about 4.8 MWh with $C_{\text{down,mean}}$ close to 0.85 kW, while O4 reaches around 4.1 MWh with a mean downward capacity of about 0.7 kW. The smallest office, O1, has a mean downward capacity of only about 0.27 kW and a cumulative shiftable energy of roughly 1.6 MWh. Nevertheless, even these modest capacities can be operationally useful when combined across several buildings and targeted at specific hours.

Kindergartens are the smallest contributors in absolute terms. Across K1–K5, the mean downward capacities range from about 0.07 to 0.36 kW, and cumulative shiftable energy lies between approximately 0.33 and 2.10 MWh per building. The largest kindergarten in flexibility terms (K2) reaches a mean downward capacity of about 0.36 kW and $E_{\text{shift,total}}$ of roughly 2.1 MWh. The others cluster between 0.07 and 0.30 kW, with cumulative flexible energy mostly below 1.8 MWh. Shorter operating windows, smaller floor areas, and lower overall heating demand explain these lower values. In the portfolio, kindergartens therefore act mainly as a small supplementary flexibility source rather than a primary provider.

In addition to the level indicators $E_{\text{shift,total}}$, $C_{\text{down,mean}}$, and $C_{\text{up,mean}}$, the analysis also computes availability indicators for each building. For several threshold values (0.25 kW, 0.5 kW, 1.0 kW,

2.0 kW), the model reports the fraction of winter candidate event hours in which the conservative downward or upward capacity exceeds that threshold, given the safety envelopes, ramp limits, and occupancy constraints. For example, for the larger schools, a downward capacity of at least 0.5 kW is available in roughly 60–75 % of winter candidate hours, while a 1.0 kW threshold is met in about 35–60 % of candidate hours; institutions show similar ranges, whereas offices and kindergartens exhibit lower availability, especially at the higher thresholds.

These availability metrics should be interpreted as temporal service indicators: they answer the question “in what proportion of potential winter event hours can the building reliably provide at least x kW of down- or up-regulation under the assumed comfort constraints?” They do not mean that the same percentage of the building’s instantaneous heating load is flexible. Instead, they describe how often a specified minimum capacity is available as a secure technical service across the considered winter period.

3.3.9.2 Safety envelopes and temperature dependence

Figure 29 summarizes the event–recovery energy balance for the representative school building (S6) by plotting mean event energy and recovery (rebound) energy versus event duration, stratified by outdoor-temperature band. Event energy increases with duration in all panels, while the recovery bars and rebound-ratio curves indicate how much of the curtailed energy is compensated within the modeled recovery horizon. In the coldest band ($-20\dots-10$ °C; panel a), the rebound ratio drops most strongly with duration, indicating that longer events are increasingly recovery-limited under cold-spell operation. In the $-10\dots0$ °C band (panel b), rebound remains near-proportional for short events but declines for longer durations, consistent with tighter comfort bounds and reduced ramp/feasibility margin as the event length increases.

In the $0\dots+10$ °C band (panel c), larger event energies are achievable and rebound remains substantial, but the rebound ratio still decreases with duration, implying that compensation does not scale one-for-one with event length. In the mildest band ($+10\dots+20$ °C; panel d), recovery energy is smaller relative to event energy and the rebound ratio is lowest overall, indicating comparatively weaker payback requirements in shoulder-season conditions. Overall, the four panels show that the apparent “firmness” of downward flexibility depends on temperature regime: colder conditions exhibit stronger recovery constraints and a sharper degradation with duration, whereas milder conditions support broader feasibility with lower relative rebound.

Figure 29: Empirical safety envelopes for a representative school building (S6). Median SHL and 5–95% bands are shown as a function of outdoor temperature, separately for occupied and unoccupied hours.

The separation between occupied and unoccupied envelopes confirms that the occupancy proxy and stratification by hour of week correctly capture schedule effects: for the same outdoor temperature, the building runs at substantially higher heating levels when occupied, and the lower envelope during unoccupied periods is wider, indicating larger scope for safe curtailment. At mild temperatures (above about 5 °C) both envelopes converge towards a narrow band close to zero, which is consistent with negligible space-heating demand and signals very limited flexibility in shoulder and summer conditions. At very low temperatures (below about -10 °C) the lower bounds rise steeply and the spread narrows, reflecting both increased comfort requirements and reduced storability; the resulting envelopes are deliberately conservative in these episodes.

Overall, the envelopes in the Figure 29 demonstrate that the flexibility framework procedure produces temperature- and occupancy-conditioned bounds that are consistent with the observed control behavior and with the expected contraction of flexibility during cold spells.

3.3.9.3 Event-level optimization and diurnal profile

As an illustrative case, Figure 30 shows a three-hour downward flexibility event for the representative school (S6). The event horizon is H_e with duration $d = 3h$, followed by a two-hour recovery horizon H_r . The red dashed curve is the day-of adjusted counterfactual baseline $\tilde{H}_t^{\text{base}}$, the blue curve is the optimized flexible heating trajectory H_t^{flex} , and the shaded band indicates the comfort-related lower bound derived from the baseline prediction interval combined with the empirical safety envelope.

Figure 30: Example 3-hour event optimization showing baseline, optimized flexible trajectory, and comfort bound.

During the event window, the optimization sustains a nearly constant reduction relative to $\tilde{h}_t^{\text{base}}$ while keeping h_t^{flex} above the comfort bound. The solution exhibits a gradual ramp-down into the event and a smooth ramp-up during recovery, consistent with the empirical ramp-rate limits and the identified thermal time constant. The rebound in the recovery horizon partially compensates for the shed energy without overshooting the baseline, thereby avoiding a secondary peak. This behavior matches the Annex-style interpretation of rebound-aware load shifting: energy is primarily redistributed in time while comfort is preserved by construction. Although the optimized trajectory is drawn as a continuous line, the decision variables are hourly; the resulting hourly power can be interpreted as an aggregate duty-cycle level over multiple heating components.

To connect the single-event example to the summary indicators reported in the tables, Figure 31 summarizes event-level outcomes for the representative school building S6 by plotting how the optimized response varies with the event start hour. For each start hour (0–23), the figure reports the mean conservative downward capacity C_{\downarrow} and upward headroom C_{\uparrow} (left axis, kW) together with the mean delivered event energy E_{event} and rebound energy E_{rec} per event (right axis, kWh/event), aggregated over all evaluated candidate events and durations. Unlike the “flexibility fingerprint” in Section 3.3.9.1, which focuses on seasonal averages and availability patterns, Figure 31 is used here to illustrate the energy-capacity trade-off and rebound behavior as a function of activation timing, highlighting hours where similar capacities lead to different net outcomes due to stronger recovery requirements (e.g., around morning warm-up).

Figure 31: Diurnal event-outcome profile for S6 aggregated across evaluated flexibility events. Mean conservative capacities C_{\downarrow} and C_{\uparrow} by event start hour are shown on the left axis (kW), and the mean delivered event energy E_{event} and rebound energy E_{rec} per event are shown on the right axis (kWh/event).

3.3.9.4 Hour-of-day and weekday patterns of flexibility

Figures 32 and 33 summarize the representative school S6 as hour-weekday heatmaps for 2024, where each cell reports the *mean available flexibility* for events starting in that hour under the corresponding day-of-week. In these plots, downward capacity C_{\downarrow} represents the available reduction headroom relative to the comfort-constrained lower bound (i.e., baseline-to-lower-envelope headroom), while upward capacity C_{\uparrow} represents the available increase headroom relative to the upper bound (i.e., upper-envelope-to-baseline headroom).

In Figure 32 (downward capacity), the available C_{\downarrow} is clearly time-dependent, with the most pronounced values concentrated around early-morning hours and selected weekend windows, and a broad tendency toward smaller values in the mid-afternoon. Weekday mornings show several high-headroom blocks consistent with pre-occupancy warm-up and start-up dynamics, when the baseline heating level is elevated while the lower bound still permits temporary setback.

Figure 32: S6 downward flexibility (kW), hour \times day heatmap. Occupancy-tightened lower envelopes suppress shed potential during school hours; nights/weekends exhibit the largest average headroom.

In contrast, the hours spanning the core part of the day show more limited average shed potential, reflecting tighter comfort constraints and reduced thermal slack. Weekend patterns are more heterogeneous, with some hours displaying elevated C_{\downarrow} despite lower occupancy, consistent with looser bounds and the absence of a strict weekday operating schedule.

In Figure 33 (upward capacity), C_{\uparrow} also follows a strong diurnal structure. The largest upward headroom appears predominantly in off-peak hours (late evening to early morning) and in a few distinct weekday/weekend blocks, indicating periods where controlled pre-heating or managed recovery can be accommodated without violating the upper bound. During the central daytime hours, upward headroom is present but typically more constrained, implying that upward activation in school hours should be scheduled conservatively to avoid coincident peaks and local overheating.

Figure 33: S6 upward flexibility (kW), hour \times day heatmap. Overnight headroom supports controlled recovery; occupied-hour headroom is present but should be applied conservatively.

Taken together, the heatmaps indicate that S6 (school) offers its most reliable flexibility in shoulder hours around the daily operating cycle (especially evening/early morning), while core daytime hours support comparatively smaller adjustments. This diurnal structure is consistent with the school’s operational schedule and with the winter load-shape evidence in Section 3.2 (morning ramp-up followed by a daytime plateau), which naturally concentrates both heating demand and actionable flexibility around the daily transition periods.

3.3.9.5 Conservative down-capacity by temperature band

Figure 34 reports the down-regulation capacity of S6 (school) as a function of hour-of-week in December, conditioned on outdoor temperature band and summarized by the P50 (median/typical) and P10 (conservative/firm) quantiles across candidate events. These capacities are obtained from the constrained flexibility optimization and therefore reflect risk-adjusted, feasibility-limited shedding potential under the adopted assumptions (baseline uncertainty, envelope bounds, ramp-rate limits, and storability/recovery constraints), rather than a simple instantaneous gap between measured load and the baseline.

In the colder band ($-10\dots0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), the P50 surface indicates that available downward regulation capacity is concentrated in a limited set of recurring hour-of-week windows, most notably around night-time and early-morning transition periods, where the school can sustain meaningful load reductions for consecutive hours. In contrast, the weekday daytime portions of the map are predominantly darker, indicating more constrained down-capacity once comfort-protection bounds and ramp-rate limits are applied. The corresponding P10 surface is lower in magnitude, as expected for a conservative quantile, but it preserves the same temporal structure: the most reliable event windows remain night-time and early morning, whereas daytime capacity is generally reduced but not identically zero. The separation between P50 and P10 reflects the effect of uncertainty (baseline error and operating-state/occupancy variability) on firm deliverability; across many hours, the P10 capacity is on the order of roughly one-half to two-thirds of the P50 level.

In the milder band ($0\dots+10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$), the down-capacity maps show broader temporal availability: usable downward capacity appears across a wider range of hours-of-week rather than being concentrated in a few narrow windows. Compared with the colder band, the P50 surface exhibits more frequent moderate firm capacity outside the main peak periods, indicating that load reduction opportunities are available in more operating situations.

Figure 34: Temperature-conditioned high-confidence conservative downward capacity $C_{down}(kW)$ for school S6 in December, shown by hour-of-week (0–167). Panels (a) and (b) correspond to the cold band ($-10\dots0\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) at the P50 (typical) and P10 (conservative) quantiles, respectively; panels (c) and (d) show the milder band ($0\dots+10\text{ }^{\circ}\text{C}$) at P50 and P10. Color indicates firm down-capacity (kW). Capacities include baseline uncertainty, flexibility safety envelopes, ramp limits, and storability constraints, and can be interpreted as typical (P50) and conservative (P10) availability for one-hour events.

The P10 surface remains lower, as expected for a conservative quantile but indicates that reliably deliverable down-capacity is less frequently close to zero during weekday daytime segments than

under colder conditions. Overall, the mild-band panels are consistent with higher risk-limited curtailment potential in milder outdoor conditions than during cold spells for the same building.

Overall, the S6 maps demonstrate how the proposed framework transforms the underlying heating operation into risk-adjusted, time-resolved flexibility capacity estimates, expressed here as hour-of-week down-capacity quantiles (P50 as *typical* availability and P10 as *conservative/firm* availability). The results also underline the importance of conditioning flexibility assessment on outdoor-temperature regime and occupancy/operating state when selecting event windows: the same hour-of-week can yield materially different firm capacity depending on whether it occurs under a cold-regime or milder-regime operating context. At portfolio level, the corresponding building-level outputs are aggregated across all 22 buildings to derive the cluster- and portfolio-level capacity–duration curves and availability surfaces reported in Section 3.3.9.

3.3.9.6 Mode mix of flexibility windows

Each candidate winter event window is classified into one of three qualitative modes based on the shape of the optimized trajectory relative to the baseline: (i) Pre-heating dominated: Most of the downward energy during the event window is enabled by increasing heating in the hours preceding the event (controlled pre-heating), then reducing heating during the event. Rebound is present but not dominant. (ii) Balanced load-shifting: Downward energy during the event and upward energy during recovery are of similar magnitude, without large peaks. Heating is essentially re-timed within the window with limited change in peak levels. (iii) Recovery-dominated: The optimization finds only limited safe curtailment during the event; most of the deviation from baseline appears as upward energy during the recovery period (strong rebound). Figure 35 visualizes how these three modes occur over the weekly operating cycle for the school S6. The dashed line is Mean Shiftable Energy per event E_{shift} indicating mode prevalence to delivered event-level flexibility.

Figure 35: S6 (School) mode mix over a week. Share of candidate events classified as pre-heating dominated, balanced load-shifting, or recovery-dominated; dashed line overlays mean shiftable energy E_{shift} (kWh/event).

Figure 36 shows the mode mix of candidate winter event windows for the school buildings. Most windows are recovery-dominated among the school buildings, and the optimized response relies primarily on rebound in the recovery horizon rather than deep curtailment during the event itself. This is consistent with Tables 7-8, which report that schools have roughly 0.64 recovery-dominated, 0.23 pre-heating, and 0.13 balanced load-shifting windows on average.

Figure 36: Mode mix of candidate winter downward-flexibility event windows for the school buildings.

The mode-mix indicators in the Table 7 and Table 8 illustrate for each building, the share of candidate event windows falling into each category. They do *not* refer to energy shares or time fractions over the entire year. Note that all optimization runs still enforce net energy-neutrality over the full event + recovery window; ‘recovery-dominated’ refers to the distribution of positive event and rebound energies under the definitions in Eqs. (10)-(12), not to a violation of net neutrality. Averaged across buildings, the cluster-level mode mix is: (i) Pre-heating windows are roughly 22-26 % of evaluated windows. (ii) Balanced load-shifting windows are roughly 10-13 %. (iii) Recovery-dominated windows: roughly 63-66 %.

Schools and offices show pre-heating shares around 23–24 %, with recovery dominating 64–65 % of windows. Kindergartens exhibit slightly higher pre-heating shares (up to ≈ 26 %) but similar recovery dominance. Institutions lie close to the portfolio average (≈ 22 % pre-heating, ≈ 13 % balanced, ≈ 65 % recovery-dominated).

This pattern indicates that the existing operation already relies heavily on implicit pre-heating and gradual recovery, especially in day-use buildings. Windows where the model can realize nearly “flat” events with limited rebound (balanced load-shifting) are relatively rare. For EFaaS scenario design, this implies that practical flexibility products will often be implemented by reshaping existing pre-heating and recovery patterns rather than introducing completely new behaviors.

Table 7: Mode mix of flexibility windows by building

Building code	cluster	share of pre-heating windows	share of balanced load-shifting windows	share of recovery-dominated windows
S1	Schools	0.302	0.202	0.496
S2	Schools	0.208	0.126	0.666
S6	Schools	0.245	0.091	0.664
S3	Schools	0.217	0.126	0.657
S4	Schools	0.212	0.129	0.658
S5	Schools	0.190	0.109	0.701
K5	Kindergartens	0.217	0.103	0.680
K1	Kindergartens	0.269	0.113	0.618
K2	Kindergartens	0.226	0.113	0.661
K3	Kindergartens	0.260	0.119	0.621
K4	Kindergartens	0.346	0.078	0.575
O1	Offices	0.278	0.091	0.631
O2	Offices	0.221	0.110	0.670
O3	Offices	0.227	0.123	0.650
O4	Offices	0.250	0.098	0.651
O5	Offices	0.237	0.098	0.665
I1	Institutions	0.223	0.119	0.658
I2	Institutions	0.215	0.133	0.652
I3	Institutions	0.209	0.128	0.663
I4	Institutions	0.220	0.123	0.657
I5	Institutions	0.215	0.122	0.663
I6	Institutions	0.233	0.119	0.648

Note: Here, ‘windows’ refer to candidate event start times t_0 (evaluated across $d \in \{1,2,3,4\}$). For interpretability, shares can be converted to an equivalent number of start-hours per week as $168 \cdot s$ (hours/week). This is an opportunity measure; windows may overlap and therefore do not represent additive service hours.

Table 8: Cluster-average mode mix of flexibility windows

cluster	mean share of pre-heating windows	mean share of balanced load-shifting windows	mean share of recovery-dominated windows
Schools	0.229	0.130	0.641
Kindergartens	0.264	0.105	0.631
Offices	0.242	0.104	0.654
Institutions	0.219	0.124	0.657

Figure 37 translates the mode shares in Tables 7–8 into an equivalent hours-per-week representation. For each building, the stacked bar sums to 168 h/week and shows how often candidate event start times fall into pre-heating dominated, balanced load-shifting, and recovery-dominated modes. This provides an intuitive weekly-scale view of the relative prevalence of each flexibility mode across the portfolio.

Figure 37: Mode mix as equivalent hours/week ($168 \times$ mode-share of candidate windows) for each building.

3.3.9.7 Seasonal availability of shiftable space heating energy

This subsection summarizes when space-heating flexibility opportunities occur over the year and how much shiftable space-heating energy they represent at cluster and portfolio level. To capture seasonality in an operationally interpretable way, we aggregate the event-level downward energy E_{event} by calendar month, yielding a seasonal availability profile that reflects both the frequency of feasible candidate windows and the typical magnitude of their reductions. Table 9 reports these monthly totals as the sum of E_{event} across candidate windows starting in each month, which we denote as monthly $E_{shift,total}$.

When monthly values are aggregated by cluster, approximately 62 to 66 percent of each cluster’s $E_{shift,total}$ for schools, offices, and institutions is associated with candidate windows starting in November to February. For kindergartens, the corresponding share is approximately 61 percent. Figure 38 shows that, within the school cluster, December and January contribute the largest monthly totals and together account for nearly one third of schools’ $E_{shift,total}$. November and February also contribute materially. Shoulder months, March, April, and October, remain meaningful but exhibit lower monthly totals. A similar seasonal pattern is observed for offices and institutions, where December and January contribute the largest shares, followed by November and February.

For kindergartens, the months with the highest heating demand, January to February and November to December, also yield the largest shiftable energy totals. However, the absolute values remain small relative to other clusters due to lower overall SHL. Table 9 reports the monthly totals for each cluster and for the full portfolio.

Figure 38: Cluster-level monthly flexible heating energy (E_{event})

Table 9: Monthly shiftable space heating energy $E_{shft, total}$ by cluster (kWh).

Month	Schools	Kindergartens	Offices	Institutions	Total
Jan	10 913	1 142	5 037	8 667	25 759
Feb	9 422	968	4 426	7 917	22 733
Mar	3 007	258	930	2 130	6 325
Apr	4 380	214	1 028	1 665	7 287
May	2 588	277	952	1 804	5 621
Jun	2 665	299	881	1 639	5 484
Jul	2 992	276	1 059	1 703	6 030
Aug	2 569	290	953	1 546	5 358
Sep	3 008	258	944	1 515	5 725
Oct	2 580	231	1 096	1 881	5 788
Nov	5 840	250	1 176	2 022	9 288
Dec	12 555	945	4 399	7 813	25 712
Total	62 519	5 408	22 881	40 302	131 110

Note: Across clusters, 60 to 70% of annual shiftable energy is concentrated in the core winter months (November to February), with negligible volumes in summer.

Overall, these results indicate that space heating based flexibility is primarily a winter service. The results therefore suggest prioritizing EFaaS activations in November to February, using shoulder months for secondary or lower intensity services, and treating summer as effectively not flexible for heating because SHL and thus technical heating flexibility are near zero. Consistent with this, Figure 38 shows that more than half of the portfolio's shiftable space heating energy is concentrated in November to February, with schools and institutions contributing the majority of the available flexibility, offices providing a secondary contribution, and kindergartens contributing marginal volumes across all months.

3.4 Role of technical outputs in EFaaS design and renewable integration

The outputs of the hybrid ICA-PLR disaggregation and the flexibility quantification framework provide a technical basis for EFaaS design in several ways. First, SHL time series and derived parameters (balance temperature, HDH slopes, response lag, thermal time constants) characterize how buildings respond to weather and occupancy, which supports the design of control strategies and EFaaS products that are compatible with comfort and service levels. Second, capacity–duration curves and availability metrics quantify the reliability of flexibility provision for different durations and temperature conditions, which is essential for sizing and valuing EFaaS products in local flexibility markets or virtual power plant configurations.

These technical outputs also serve as inputs to renewable integration and technology optimization studies conducted by partners such as RTU. For example, technology sizing models for photovoltaics, heat pumps, biomass boilers, and thermal storage can use SHL profiles and flexibility envelopes to evaluate how different technology portfolios interact with demand response and how much additional flexibility can be unlocked by storage. Similarly, business-model analyses can use the quantified flexibility and availability to assess revenue streams and risk profiles for EFaaS contracts under national tariff schemes.

The common framework described in this section is therefore the methodological core of D3.1. The following sections apply and extend this framework in specific living labs, starting with the Verdal public-building case in Norway.

3.4.1 Link between SHL/flexibility outputs and technology/portfolio design

The SHL disaggregation and flexibility quantification results produced for the municipal building stock in Verdal provide design-relevant parameters that can be mapped to technology selection, sizing, and operational constraints in energy-flexibility-as-a-service (EFaaS) implementations. In particular, the day-of adjusted reference heating profile and associated uncertainty bounds define the “business-as-usual” operating range, while the risk-limited flexibility envelopes and capacity–duration curves quantify (i) feasible upward/downward modulation magnitudes, (ii) activation durations, and (iii) the corresponding recovery requirements needed to preserve energy neutrality and comfort constraints. In line with the IEA EBC Annex 67 definition, building energy flexibility is understood as the capability of a building or building cluster to adjust its demand and on-site generation in response to grid requirements while maintaining indoor conditions and user needs [51]. Accordingly, the hybrid ICA-PLR framework and the flexibility methodology in Sections 3.2 and 3.3 translate hourly smart-meter and weather data into an operational description of this capability through SHL time series, baseline models, and flexibility indicators such as capacity–duration curves, rebound energy, and availability metrics. These indicators align with capacity- and power-change-oriented metrics commonly used in the energy-flexibility literature for residential and non-residential buildings [3].

From a technology and portfolio perspective, these outputs define the feasible operating space within which candidate supply technologies and control schemes must function. SHL profiles and baseline models determine the magnitude and temporal structure of thermal demand that must be met by combinations of heat pumps, direct electric heaters, district heating interfaces, and thermal storage. Prior studies on heat-pump-integrated thermal energy storage and power-to-heat solutions show that achievable demand response and peak-shaving potential depend strongly on the interaction between heating-demand profiles, storage capacity, and control strategy [52], [53]. By providing data-driven SHL profiles and risk-limited flexibility envelopes at both building and portfolio level, this deliverable offers a realistic representation of the demand-side boundary conditions that can be used in optimization and techno-economic assessment to size equipment, evaluate controllability, and quantify energy, economic, and emissions impacts.

Practically, the SHL/flexibility outputs support three design steps that bridge quantification to implementation:

1. Screening and prioritization of candidate buildings/services. Buildings with consistently higher short-duration capacity (e.g., 1–4 h), robust availability across winter temperature bands, and repeatable recovery behavior represent stronger candidates for near-term flexibility service provisioning. This helps narrow deployment to the assets most likely to deliver contractual services with acceptable operational risk.

2. Control-horizon and constraint design for operational strategies. Capacity–duration behavior, empirical ramp limits, and recovery horizons inform the feasible control horizon and how quickly and by how much heat pumps and electric heaters can be ramped without violating comfort or technical limits. Availability metrics across temperature bands indicate when flexibility is most reliably accessible. These elements are directly translatable into supervisory-control constraints and scheduling rules for coordinated operation of heat pumps, thermal storage, rooftop photovoltaics, and potentially wind generation to provide DSF and participate in local or wholesale market services [54].
3. Sizing guidance for enabling technologies. The combination of (i) required modulation magnitude, (ii) activation duration, and (iii) recovery signatures provide indicative requirements for actuator capacity (e.g., heat pump electrical/thermal capacity) and for storage power/energy ratings needed to deliver targeted flexibility products reliably. In this sense, the flexibility envelope and capacity–duration curve function as data-driven “design constraints” for sizing and for verifying that candidate portfolios can deliver services under realistic demand conditions.

Finally, the SHL and flexibility outputs are directly relevant for EFaaS and related service-oriented business models. Flexibility- and energy-as-a-service concepts rely on quantifying the amount, timing, and reliability of flexible capacity that can be offered by aggregators on behalf of buildings and prosumers, and on linking this capability to contractual products and remuneration schemes [55], [56]. In this context, the Verdal framework provides the quantitative backbone for specifying EFaaS products (e.g., morning peak-shaving services with defined capacities and durations), valuing investments in enabling technologies (heat pumps and thermal storage), and comparing alternative technology portfolios in terms of both energy performance and flexibility potential. These links are intended as operationally actionable, data-driven inputs to WP3 scenario design and technology assessment in PERSIST. Final technology selection and sizing should additionally reflect building-specific comfort requirements, hydraulic constraints, tariff structures, and the control architecture available at each site.

3.4.2 Methodology for equipment selection and control of a synergetic HPSS

To complement the data-driven flexibility characterisation of the HiØF case buildings, this section summarises an optimisation-based retrofitting and control study for a renewable-based heat and power supply system (HPSS). The purpose is to illustrate how quantified flexibility potentials (capacity, duration, and recovery) can be translated into (i) equipment sizing decisions (renewables, heat pumps, thermal storage) and (ii) supervisory control strategies that maximise self-consumption and economic value. The presented study considers dedicated heat storage as the primary flexibility buffer and does not explicitly model building thermal inertia as an additional storage mechanism. RTU has developed and tested a methodology for selecting and controlling a synergetic heat and power supply system (HPSS) for a multi-story apartment building (MSAB). The work is motivated by the high energy use and emissions from the European building stock and by the need to unlock DSF in buildings.

This methodology has been developed for equipment selection and control for a synergetic heat and power supply system (HPSS) to a multi-storey apartment building (MSAB) considering the aforementioned sources of DSF. In particular, the envisioned HPSS includes renewable power sources (RPSs), heat pumps (HPs), heat storage (HS) with an integrated electric heater (EH) and a district heating network (DHN). The presence of a DHN, thus, also existence of hot-water-circulation-based (HWCB) heating is assumed because the data for testing was immediately available for a type of Soviet-era MSAB common in Latvia and refurbishment of apartment buildings is topical not only in Latvia, but also in Europe. A study testing various approaches to the selection and control of equipment constituting the HPSS demonstrated that the methodology can effectively schedule operation, select optimal equipment portfolio considering the scheduling, and that the resulting HPSS can provide economic gains [49]. This profit is achieved due to several reasons: energy savings provided by utilisation of HPs, local renewable power generated by rooftop RPSs, and DSF. This energy flexibility arises from instalment of the HS as well as introduction (in case of the studied MSABs) of power-to-heat (P2H) technologies allowing intersectoral synergy.

Currently HWCB heating that is similar to ones used in DHNs in Latvia and often in other Eastern European countries is not utilised for buildings in the Verdal community where, similarly to large parts of Norway, power and heat demand is met using solely electricity [57]. However, change to HWCB heating is considered for individual buildings as one of perspective solutions physically enabling significant DSF in buildings of Verdal community, which is necessary, if provision of an EFaaS is desired. Furthermore, change to such a heating system would facilitate integration of HPs with their high coefficient of performance (COP) and more affordable hot water tank (HWT) HS. The HPSS considered by the methodology will also be adapted when studying Verdal to at least take into account nonexistence of a DHN.

3.4.2.1 Goals and the structure of the study for development and testing of the methodology

The goals of the study for development and testing of the methodology are

- development of the methodology for selection and control of equipment for a synergetic HPSS based on an existing method for modelling and optimisation of power supply to apartment buildings [58],
- testing of the developed methodology, when utilised for a MSAB common in Latvia;
- evaluation of performance of the synergetic HPSS for the MSAB under study;
- fostering of the retrofitting of energy supply systems of MSABs, improving their sustainability by the demonstration of the potential of the studied HPSS.

In order to achieve the stated goals, modelling of the HPSS is described in Section 3.4.2.2, and the analyzed approaches for control and equipment sizing are presented in Section 3.4.2.3. Next, results and main findings of the study are provided in Section 3.4.2.4.

3.4.2.2 Modelling of the heat and power supply system

This section describes the technological options considered for the HPSS under study and their interactions.

The retrofitted HPSS analysed in the study in its fullest form is presented in Figure 39. The system includes a HWT HS, acting as a buffer for space heating and domestic hot water (DHW) supply, which can be simultaneously or separately charged by air-source HPs, an integrated EH both powered either by RPSs or a power grid (PG), and a DHN.

Figure 39: The configuration of the analyzed retrofitted heat and power supply system [49]

In this system, the power demand is met by local renewable generation and/or the PG. HS is the only considered ES, as lithium-ion batteries or hydrogen storage involve significantly larger investments for a MSAB already having a HWCBS space heating. Moreover, building thermal

inertia is not considered as there is limited options for significantly lowering indoor temperatures for several public buildings in the Verdal municipality, such as kindergartens. While HPs also represent sizable investment costs, their high COP may be invaluable for covering as large a portion of the significant heat load characteristic of Latvia or even colder places like Norway, as possible with limited space for installations. Moreover, the HPs are the main source of primary energy savings in this energy supply system.

The studied HPSS, in its essence, is described by two energy balances that are schematically shown in Figure 40.

Figure 40: The energy balances of the analysed retrofitted heat and power supply system [49]

The testing of developed methodology utilises the following input data for 2023:

- measurements of generated electric energy for a real photovoltaic (PV) installation in Riga,
- wind speed measurements from a meteorological station in Riga combined with a polynomial approximation of output power curve for a vertical wind turbine (WT),
- measured ambient temperature for calculation of COP of HPs,
- average heat tariff from the local DHN operator and hourly Nord Pool spot electricity prices,
- approximate costs for procurement and installation of equipment of various capacities,
- data on energy demand shown in an aggregated form in Figure 41 for a type of Soviet-era MSAB common in Latvia.

Figure 41: Monthly energy demand of the case study MSAB during 2023: for space heating, DHW preparation, and electric loads (Power) [49]

3.4.2.3 Optimisation and control of the heat and power supply system

In conjunction with an evaluation of the potential of the described HPSS, several methodological setups for equipment selection (sizing) and control (scheduling) have been analysed in the study. These setups are variants of the methodology under considerations. These include a baseline (reference) setup S1 of an unrenovated MSAB without changes and ones considering refurbishment (S2-S5). Their main characteristics are summarised in Figure 42.

Equipment sizing: Existing power grid connection and existing DHN connection. No additional equipment.		S1 (Base)	
Operation scheduling: Supply from existing networks upon demand			
Equipment sizing: Optimisation: GA Objective: max (NPV) Variables: rated power of RPSs and HPs, and volume of the HWT	S2	Equipment sizing: Optimisation: GA Objective: max (NPV and SSR) Variables: rated power of RPSs and HPs, and volume of the HWT	S3
Operation scheduling: Control: conventional Principle: maximally cover energy demand with local RPSs, HPs, EH, and HS heat, charge HS, if beneficial, and sell excess power		Operation scheduling: Control: conventional Principle: maximally cover energy demand with local RPSs, HPs, EH, and HS heat, charge HS, if beneficial, and sell excess power	
Equipment sizing: Optimisation: GA Objective: max (NPV) Variables: rated power of RPSs and HPs, and volume of the HWT	S4	Equipment sizing: Optimisation: GA Objective: max (NPV and SSR) Variables: rated power of RPSs and HPs, and volume of the HWT	S5
Operation scheduling: Control: gradient-based optimisation Objectives: min (TDC) Variables: discharge/charge of HS, use of power generated by RPS		Operation scheduling: Control: gradient-based optimisation Objectives: min (TDC) Variables: discharge/charge of HS, use of power generated by RPS	

Figure 42: A summary of the analysed methodological setups S1–S5, including genetic algorithm (GA); net present value (NPV); self-sufficiency rate (SSR); total daily costs (TDC) [49]

The “conventional” or rules- and settings-based control for hourly scheduling, first, covers as much power demand of the MSAB as possible using output of the RPS installed and calculates, if any renewable electric energy remains available for heating purposes.

Second, when there is remaining locally generated energy, it is allocated to HPs and EH (prioritising HPs) based on the quantity of renewable energy available and the amount electric energy both types of P2H equipment can consume during the given hour considering limitations of the HPSS.

Third, any excess renewable electric energy that cannot be utilised by the MSAB is sold back to the PG. However, use of net billing or net metering systems [59] or similar support scheme might be used instead based on the particular situation and regulation.

Fourth, if supply from local RPS is insufficient, power is bought from PG to meet power demand and also for heat production, when the tariff for heat from DHN sufficiently exceeds the tariff for electricity.

Fifth, it is determined whether heat from HPs and the EH can meet the net heat demand and charge the HS, if the produced heat exceeds demand. Alternatively, HS is discharging when the heat from P2H technologies is insufficient. Finally, if there is still heat deficit, it is met by buying heat from the DHN.

While the study showed that the optimisation-based smart control outperformed the conventional one, its adoption might be required when optimising the composition of a HPSS for larger number of buildings due to resulting computational burden.

The limitation for decision variables in the study can be mentioned for contextualising of results in Table 10. These are 0-32 kW for the whole RPSs installation (PV panels and WTs) based on the roof area of the MSAB, 0-120 kW for HPs and 25-250 kWh for the HS based on the space in the basement.

3.4.2.4 Analysis of the obtained results

In order to test the performance of the methodology, first, the correct operation of the optimisation performing the equipment sizing (selection) is verified by plotting an optimum point for all methodological setups and points for all potential equipment combinations for setups S2 and S3 in SSR, NPV coordinates (Fig. 40). At least one of these two parameters constitutes objective functions for optimisation utilised.

Figure 43 clearly demonstrates that the equipment set selected by the setup S2 represents the best solution solely in terms of NPV. An optimum point for equipment selected applying S3 also appears credible in Figure 43 as increase in SSR comes at minimal loss in NPV. S3 optimum was verified also by separately calculating objective function (a combination of SSR and a NPV relative to one obtained for S2 optimum) values. Optimum points obtained applying setups S4 and S5 with smart control have not been separately verified in such a way due to large computation time that would be required to optimise operation for all possible equipment sets with a hourly timestep throughout a full year. However, as expected, the performance of HPSS is significantly better, when applying S4 and S5 compared to use of setups S2 and S3 with the conventional control. Furthermore, change of control approach is unlikely to affect efficiency of the optimisation selecting between equipment options.

Figure 43: The solution space for setups S2 and S3 in SSR and NPV coordinates indicating averaged upper and lower bounds of the solution space (zone maximum and minimum), optimum points for the methodological setups (S2, S3, S4, and S5), the Pareto line for setup S3 (SSR+NPV Pareto), and the values for all the variants of an equipment portfolio when conventional control is applied (All) [49]

In addition to testing of optimisation sizing the HPSS, Figure 43 and a more detailed analysis of its results indicated the following [49]:

- the limited roof area of a single MSAB does not permit reaching SSR of even 50 %, if both heat and power demand is considered,
- the NPV values of the solution space rise alongside the SSRs until a certain peak, after which any changes in the composition of equipment used fail to yield sufficient cost savings relative to additional investments, which is evidenced by degrading NPV values,
- while most equipment portfolios can be economically justifiable, those characterised by an oversized HWT HS (above 125 kWh) and by an absence of HPs may not achieve return of investments even after the period of 20 years assumed in the study.

The considered control approaches are tested by comparison between the simulated operation of the HPSS with rules of the conventional control and between performance of the smart (optimisation-based) control relative to the conventional one. For illustration Figures 44 and 45 demonstrate operation scheduled by the conventional control during a winter week. These figures immediately demonstrate that the conventional control adheres to energy balances and limits of equipment selected (Table 10). Furthermore, Figure 44 shows how the conventional control has bought power for P2H conversion during relatively low-price hours, e.g., 3–6 and 72–81, during most of which the ratio of tariffs for power and heat from utilities is between 1.5 and 1. Thus, in the heat balance (Figure 45), the effect is seen as replacing the supply from the DHN with heat from HPs. However, when the tariff ratio (for power from PG to heat from DHN) falls below 1 during high-demand hours, such as 46–48, 72, and 100, activation of the EH also becomes

justifiable. As expected, when electricity is relatively expensive the conventional control avoided buying power for heat production, meeting the heat demand with HS as much as possible before buying heat from the DHN. In this regard, the only time heat is provided by HPs during high electricity prices is the second half of the first day when there is some renewable power remaining for heat production.

Figure 44: An electric energy balance for a winter week (20/02/2023–26/02/2023) obtained using conventional control with the optimal equipment portfolio for setup S2 demonstrating the resident demand and the net demand; the composition of sources supplying it and the ratio between the tariffs for power and heat [49]

Figure 45: A heat balance for the winter week, obtained by using conventional control with the optimal equipment portfolio for setup S2, displaying the total heat demand and the composition of the sources supplying it (negative values for HS indicate charging) [49]

Operation of the HPSS scheduled by the smart control for the same week is provided in Figures 46 and 47, which also demonstrate the adherence to energy balances and equipment limits. When

comparing the electric energy balances for the winter week shown in Figures 43. and 45., one can immediately notice how the smart control is buying power for heat production much more frequently, avoiding this option only when the tariff ratio approaches or exceeds the COP of the HPs. The second evident difference is the sophisticated use of the HS (Figure 47), which is not only charged and discharged more steadily, while the smart control waits for a more favourable tariff ratio and maximises charging with HPs, e.g., at hours 1–3 and 89–100. Moreover, HS operation is coordinated better with HPs and the EH, helping to extract benefits even from local price fluctuations, e.g., hours 46–56 and 72–83.

Figure 46: An electric energy balance for the winter week obtained by using smart control with the optimal equipment portfolio for setup S4, demonstrating the resident demand and the net demand, composition of sources supplying it, the ratio between the tariffs for power and heat, and the COP of the HPs [49]

Figure 47: A heat balance for the winter week obtained by using smart control with the optimal equipment portfolio for setup S4, displaying the total heat demand and the composition of sources supplying it (negative values for HS indicate charging) [49]

Compared to the conventional control, the EH is utilised more cautiously, preferring slower charging of the HS by the more efficient HPs, e.g., at hours 72–82, or by supplementing at least part of the heat demand that is not met by the HPs with HS discharges during momentary price spikes, e.g., at hours 46–56. These changes in control actions allow for heat to be mostly or fully supplied by the HPs and HS discharges during the majority of hours in the winter week.

During a summer week analysed in the development and testing study the HS is charged and discharged more often with a lower magnitude as well, thus making it possible to await a further fall in the tariff ratio, which is not a case for the conventional control. Furthermore, during the summer, the smart control also aims for a coincidence between a drop in the heat demand for DHW and a peak in PV output during the midday before charging the HS.

Together these differences demonstrate the capability of the smart control to better leverage the available energy flexibility for economic gains as indicated in Figure 43 and Table 10 as well. While it is not analysed in detail the implicit DSF is evident as shown by adaptation of electricity use for heating to energy tariffs as well as to availability of renewable power, shifting of the heat demand by HS to a more advantageous time, and changes in use of electric heating technologies based on the energy tariffs.

A part of the main results of the study is assembled in Table 10.

Table 10: A summary of the main results of the study [49].

Parameters	Methodological setup				
	S1	S2	S3	S4	S5
P_{PVR} , kW	0	20	16	20	20
P_{WTR} , kW	0	12	16	12	12
P_{HPR} , kW	0	80	80	80	80
Q_{HSmax} , kWh	0	50	100	50	50
EB_E , kEUR/year	6.83	11.30	11.67	17.20	17.20
EB_Q , kEUR/year	28.58	13.06	12.09	5.76	5.76
C_{IN} , kEUR	0	89.31	100.31	89.31	89.31
NPV, kEUR	–	70.73	69.46	90.88	90.88
PP, years	–	9.6	10.3	8.3	8.3
SSR, p.u.	0	0.3509	0.3689	0.4666	0.4666
SCR, p.u.	0	1	1	1	1
EUI, kWh/m ² /year	188.55	122.38	118.99	100.57	100.57
ΔEn , MWh/year (%)	0 (0 *)	126.24 (76.79 *)	132.71 (77.35 *)	167.86 (82.54 *)	167.86 (82.54 *)

* Percentage of the total energy saving achieved by HPs.

Table 10 includes the total rated power of the installed PV panels, WTs, and HPs (P_{PVR} , P_{WTR} , and P_{HPR}), the HS capacity of the selected HWT (Q_{HSmax}), the energy bill (EB) for electricity (EB_E), which takes into account the power exported to the PG, EB for heat (EB_Q), which represents only the energy cost savings, the net investment costs (C_{IN}), NPV, the payback period (PP), SSR, self-

consumption rate (SCR), annual energy use intensity (EUI), total energy savings (ΔEn) with an indication of what proportion is achieved due to HPs (primary energy savings).

Additional noteworthy observations that can be made based on the results in Table 10 include:

- the main source of energy and cost savings for the studied HPSS, when applied to the MSAB in Latvia, is the shift of energy supply from the DHN to the RPSs and the PG. This is evident, when comparing EB values and a ratio EB_Q/EB_E that is 4.18, 1.16, and 0.33 when applying S1, S2 and S4, respectively,
- the smart control utilised in setups S4 and S5 achieved better profitability, self-sustainability and higher primary energy savings, even when selecting the same equipment set as S2,
- when using the smart control, the efficiency of the scheduling can result in the same equipment set both, when optimising equipment sizing for maximum NPV and when NPV is being balanced with SSR.

4 Conclusion

Deliverable D3.1 has established a common, measurement-based EFaaS framework that links hourly smart-meter data, hybrid SHL disaggregation, and uncertainty-aware flexibility quantification to practical EFaaS scenarios for Verdal's public-building portfolio. By delivering validated SHL estimates, portfolio-level flexibility envelopes, and technology- and business-model-relevant indicators, D3.1 provides the technical core of WP3 and a reusable reference for subsequent PERSIST WPs and living labs.

Regarding Section 3.2, the hybrid ICA-PLR framework has demonstrated that reliable SHL estimates can be obtained from hourly main-meter data in a cold-climate municipal portfolio with only limited sub-metering. Validation against five submetered buildings shows hourly R^2 values of around 0.82, with further improvement under daily and weekly aggregation, and confirms that the method preserves physically meaningful temperature sensitivities, balance temperatures, and shoulder-season tapering. Portfolio results indicate that approximately 2.91 GWh, or 42% of total electricity use in 2024, is attributable to space heating, rising to about 54% in the core winter months, with institutions and the largest schools dominating both absolute and relative heating contributions. Cluster-level profiles reveal clear diurnal and weekly patterns, including pronounced morning warm-up and evening setback in day-use buildings and steadier but higher baselines in institutions. These findings support the recommendation to use weekly winter aggregates as the primary reporting resolution, with uncertainty bands of about ± 20 –25% at hourly scale and tighter intervals at aggregated scales, and confirm that the hybrid ICA-PLR method offers a transferable, portfolio-ready approach for separating SHL and NHL in PERSIST living labs.

Regarding Section 3.3, the flexibility characterization and quantification framework translates the disaggregated SHL series into Annex-aligned, operationally meaningful indicators of capacity, duration, shiftable energy, rebound and availability, using a six-stage pipeline that combines baseline ensembles, non-intrusive occupancy proxies, storability estimates, safety envelopes, empirical ramp limits, and chance-constrained, energy-neutral optimization. Applied to the Verdal portfolio, this framework yields building-, cluster- and portfolio-level capacity–duration curves and availability surfaces that are explicitly conditioned on temperature and occupancy. The cumulative event-level indicator $E_{shift,total}$ shows that about 131 MWh of heating energy – roughly 4.5 % of annual SHL – could in principle be temporarily reduced and later recovered under the imposed safety constraints if all candidate winter windows were activated once, with nearly half of this volume provided by schools and about one third by institutions, while offices play a secondary role and kindergartens contribute only marginally. Mode-mix statistics reveal that most candidate windows are recovery-dominated, with only 10–13 % resembling near-flat, balanced shifting, confirming that practical EFaaS products will need to reshape existing pre-heating and recovery patterns rather than rely on idealized rectangular events. Seasonal aggregation shows that 60–70 % of cumulative flexible energy arises from events in November–February, with negligible summer volumes, underlining that SHL-based flexibility is primarily a winter service. Hour-of-

week and temperature-stratified capacity maps further demonstrate that firm downward flexibility is largest and most reliable during night-time and early-morning hours in schools, offices and institutions, especially under moderate cold, whereas cold spells tighten envelopes, shorten feasible durations and reduce conservative capacities. Overall, Section 3.3 establishes an uncertainty-aware, portfolio-ready FLEX-SHL procedure that converts hourly SHL estimates into operationally meaningful, temperature-conditioned flexibility envelopes and availability metrics, providing a quantitative bridge between measured building performance and EFaaS product and portfolio design in Verdal.

Regarding Section 3.4, the technical outputs from Sections 3.2 and 3.3 are shown to be directly useful for technology portfolio design, renewable integration, and EFaaS business models. SHL profiles, thermal time constants, and flexibility envelopes define the operating envelope within which candidate combinations of heat pumps, electric heaters, thermal storage, rooftop renewables, and (where relevant) district heating must perform. The HPSS methodology developed and tested by RTU on a Latvian multi-story apartment building illustrates how these demand-side descriptors can be used to size equipment, design smart control strategies, and quantify economic performance, including energy savings, self-sufficiency, and NPV. The comparison between conventional and optimization-based control highlights the added value of exploiting flexibility explicitly, for example by shifting P2H operation in response to time-varying tariffs and renewable output. Section 3.4 therefore demonstrates how the EFaaS framework can inform cross-sectoral designs that couple electricity, heat, and storage, and provides a template for extending the Verdal experience to residential buildings and other living labs in D3.2 and related deliverables.

References:

- [1] B. K. Sovacool *et al.*, “Decarbonizing household heating: Reviewing demographics, geography and low-carbon practices and preferences in five European countries,” *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 139, p. 110703, Apr. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2020.110703.
- [2] “Energy Performance of Buildings Directive.” Accessed: Nov. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://energy.ec.europa.eu/topics/energy-efficiency/energy-performance-buildings/energy-performance-buildings-directive_en
- [3] J. Vivian, U. Chiodarelli, G. Emmi, and A. Zarrella, “A sensitivity analysis on the heating and cooling energy flexibility of residential buildings,” *Sustain. Cities Soc.*, vol. 52, p. 101815, Jan. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.scs.2019.101815.
- [4] “SET Plan progress report 2022.” Accessed: Nov. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://setis.ec.europa.eu/set-plan-progress-report-2022_en
- [5] K. Yang, R. Zou, W. Zhang, X. Zeng, Z. Li, and J. Guo, “Comprehensive review of Positive Energy Districts: Multidimensional analysis of energy, economic, social, and environmental aspects,” *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 217, p. 115740, Jul. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2025.115740.
- [6] V. Albert-Seifried *et al.*, “Definitions of Positive Energy Districts: A Review of the Status Quo and Challenges,” 2022, pp. 493–506. doi: 10.1007/978-981-16-6269-0_41.
- [7] S. Ø. Jensen *et al.*, “IEA EBC Annex 67 Energy Flexible Buildings,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 155, Nov. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2017.08.044.
- [8] A. Marszal-Pomianowska *et al.*, “International Energy Agency - Characterization of Energy Flexibility in Buildings: Energy in Buildings and Communities Programme Annex 67 Energy Flexible Buildings,” Danish Technological Institute, Report, Dec. 2019.
- [9] A. Michaelis, M. Schneider, and M. Weibelzahl, “Designing local flexibility markets: A toolbox for policymakers and market operators,” *Energy*, vol. 329, p. 136051, Aug. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2025.136051.
- [10] F. Zornow, S. Talari, W. Ketter, M. Ebrahimi, and M. Shafie-khah, “Local Flexibility Markets and Business Models,” in *Trading in Local Energy Markets and Energy Communities: Concepts, Structures and Technologies*, M. Shafie-khah and A. S. Gazafroudi, Eds., Cham: Springer International Publishing, 2023, pp. 181–220. doi: 10.1007/978-3-031-21402-8_7.
- [11] PERSIST Consortium, “PERSIST.” Accessed: Nov. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://dutpartnership.eu/projects/persist>
- [12] “Nordic Energy Technology Perspectives 2016,” Ea Energianalyse. Accessed: Nov. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.ea-energianalyse.dk/en/publications/nordic-energy-technology-perspectives-2016/>

- [13] M. Hofmann, S. Bjarghov, and S. Nessa, “Norwegian hourly residential electricity demand data with consumer characteristics during the European energy crisis,” *Data Brief*, vol. 51, p. 109687, Dec. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.dib.2023.109687.
- [14] M. Hofmann and K. B. Lindberg, “Evidence of households’ demand flexibility in response to variable hourly electricity prices – Results from a comprehensive field experiment in Norway,” *Energy Policy*, vol. 184, 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.enpol.2023.113821.
- [15] I. Hanssen-Bauer *et al.*, *Climate in Norway 2100*. 2017.
- [16] MET, “Norwegian Meteorological Institute,” [met.no/en/weather-and-climate](https://www.met.no/en/weather-and-climate). Accessed: Nov. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.met.no/en/weather-and-climate>
- [17] A. Keçebaş, H. Gökgedik, E. Y. Gürbüz, and M. Ertürk, “Energy and exergy-based degree-hours in estimation of heat requirements for heating and cooling purposes,” *Energy Convers. Manag.*, vol. 307, p. 118347, May 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.enconman.2024.118347.
- [18] Y. Zhu and S. Lu, *Load profile disaggregation by Blind source separation: A wavelets-assisted independent component analysis approach*, vol. 2014. 2014, p. 5. doi: 10.1109/PESGM.2014.6938947.
- [19] H. Kim *et al.*, “An ICA-Based HVAC Load Disaggregation Method Using Smart Meter Data,” Sep. 19, 2022, *arXiv*: arXiv:2209.09165. doi: 10.48550/arXiv.2209.09165.
- [20] H. Komatsu and O. Kimura, “A combination of SOM-based operating time estimation and simplified disaggregation for SME buildings using hourly energy consumption data,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 201, pp. 118–133, Oct. 2019, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2019.07.036.
- [21] K. X. Perez *et al.*, “Nonintrusive disaggregation of residential air-conditioning loads from sub-hourly smart meter data,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 81, pp. 316–325, Oct. 2014, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2014.06.031.
- [22] A. Reilly and O. Kinnane, “The impact of thermal mass on building energy consumption,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 198, pp. 108–121, Jul. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.04.024.
- [23] M. Schaffer, J. Widén, J. E. Vera-Valdés, A. Marszal-Pomianowska, and T. S. Larsen, “Disaggregation of total energy use into space heating and domestic hot water: A city-scale suited approach,” *Energy*, vol. 291, p. 130351, Mar. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2024.130351.
- [24] S. Verbeke and A. Audenaert, “Thermal inertia in buildings: A review of impacts across climate and building use,” *Renew. Sustain. Energy Rev.*, vol. 82, pp. 2300–2318, Feb. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.rser.2017.08.083.
- [25] A. Zoha, A. Gluhak, M. A. Imran, and S. Rajasegarar, “Non-Intrusive Load Monitoring Approaches for Disaggregated Energy Sensing: A Survey,” *Sensors*, vol. 12, no. 12, Art. no. 12, Dec. 2012, doi: 10.3390/s121216838.

- [26] N. Businelli, “2024 Assessment of Demand Response and Advanced Metering,” 2024.
- [27] J. Kissock, “Inverse Modeling Toolkit: Numerical Algorithms for Best-Fit Variable-Base Degree Day and Change Point Models,” Jan. 2003, Accessed: Oct. 02, 2025. [Online]. Available: https://www.academia.edu/85910983/Inverse_Modeling_Toolkit_Numerical_Algorithms_for_Best_Fit_Variable_Base_Degree_Day_and_Change_Point_Models
- [28] M. T. Paulus, D. E. Claridge, and C. Culp, “Algorithm for automating the selection of a temperature dependent change point model,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 87, pp. 95–104, Jan. 2015, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2014.11.033.
- [29] “ASHRAE Guideline 14-2014: Energy, Demand, Water Savings,” studylib.net. Accessed: Aug. 20, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://studylib.net/doc/27529665/ashrae-d-86835>
- [30] A. Kipping and E. Trømborg, “Modeling and disaggregating hourly electricity consumption in Norwegian dwellings based on smart meter data,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 118, pp. 350–369, Apr. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.02.042.
- [31] M. Liang, Y. Meng, N. Lu, D. Lubkeman, and A. Kling, *HVAC load Disaggregation using Low-resolution Smart Meter Data*. 2019, p. 5. doi: 10.1109/ISGT.2019.8791578.
- [32] K. X. Perez, K. Cetin, M. Baldea, and T. F. Edgar, “Development and analysis of residential change-point models from smart meter data,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 139, pp. 351–359, Mar. 2017, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2016.12.084.
- [33] D.-W. Kim, K.-U. Ahn, H. Shin, and S.-E. Lee, “Simplified Weather-Related Building Energy Disaggregation and Change-Point Regression: Heating and Cooling Energy Use Perspective,” *Buildings*, vol. 12, no. 10, p. 1717, Oct. 2022, doi: 10.3390/buildings12101717.
- [34] Y. Ding, H. Brattebø, and N. Nord, “A systematic approach for data analysis and prediction methods for annual energy profiles: An example for school buildings in Norway,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 247, p. 111160, Sep. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2021.111160.
- [35] A. Hyvärinen and E. Oja, “Independent component analysis: algorithms and applications,” *Neural Netw.*, vol. 13, no. 4, pp. 411–430, Jun. 2000, doi: 10.1016/S0893-6080(00)00026-5.
- [36] “Independent Component Analysis: A Tutorial Introduction | MIT Press eBooks | IEEE Xplore.” Accessed: Aug. 20, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://ieeexplore.ieee.org/book/6267342>
- [37] R. G. Junker *et al.*, “Characterizing the energy flexibility of buildings and districts,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 225, pp. 175–182, Sep. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2018.05.037.
- [38] A. Kathirgamanathan *et al.*, “Towards standardising market-independent indicators for quantifying energy flexibility in buildings,” *Energy Build.*, vol. 220, p. 110027, Aug. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.enbuild.2020.110027.

- [39] “IEA EBC || Annex 82 || Energy Flexible Buildings Towards Resilient Low Carbon Energy Systems || IEA EBC || Annex 82.” Accessed: Nov. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://annex82.iea-ebc.org/>
- [40] J. Le Dréau and P. Heiselberg, “Energy flexibility of residential buildings using short term heat storage in the thermal mass,” *Energy*, vol. 111, pp. 991–1002, Sep. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2016.05.076.
- [41] S. Stinner, K. Huchtemann, and D. Müller, “Quantifying the operational flexibility of building energy systems with thermal energy storages,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 181, pp. 140–154, Nov. 2016, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2016.08.055.
- [42] K. Coughlin, M. A. Piette, C. Goldman, and S. Kiliccote, “Estimating Demand Response Load Impacts: Evaluation of Baseline Load Models for Non-Residential Buildings in California,” May 2008, Accessed: Nov. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://escholarship.org/uc/item/8jx6t5q9>
- [43] Z. Liang, Y. Liu, Y. Xu, and T. Wagner, “Bayesian change point quantile regression approach to enhance the understanding of shifting phytoplankton-dimethyl sulfide relationships in aquatic ecosystems,” *Water Res.*, vol. 201, p. 117287, Aug. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.watres.2021.117287.
- [44] Q. Meng *et al.*, “Change-point multivariable quantile regression to explore effect of weather variables on building energy consumption and estimate base temperature range,” *Sustain. Cities Soc.*, vol. 53, p. 101900, Feb. 2020, doi: 10.1016/j.scs.2019.101900.
- [45] A. Mirfin, X. Xiao, and M. W. Jack, “TOWST: A physics-informed statistical model for building energy consumption with solar gain,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 369, p. 123488, Sep. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2024.123488.
- [46] P. Kohlhepp, L. Gröll, and V. Hagenmeyer, “Characterization of Aggregated Building Heating, Ventilation, and Air Conditioning Load as a Flexibility Service Using Gray-Box Modeling,” *Energy Technol.*, vol. 9, no. 9, p. 2100251, 2021, doi: 10.1002/ente.202100251.
- [47] J. Hensen and R. Lamberts, *Building Performance Simulation for Design and Operation 2ND EDITION*. 2019. doi: 10.1201/9780429402296.
- [48] S. Yang, H. O. Gao, and F. You, “Demand flexibility and cost-saving potentials via smart building energy management: Opportunities in residential space heating across the US,” *Adv. Appl. Energy*, vol. 14, p. 100171, Jul. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.adapen.2024.100171.
- [49] K. Jevgenijs, Z. Ivars, A. Mutule, and P. Lubova, “Optimised Sizing and Control of Non-Invasive Retrofit Options for More Sustainable Heat and Power Supply to Multi-Storey Apartment Buildings.” Accessed: Nov. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.mdpi.com/2071-1050/17/1/236>

- [50] C. Finck, R. Li, R. Kramer, and W. Zeiler, “Quantifying demand flexibility of power-to-heat and thermal energy storage in the control of building heating systems,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 209, pp. 409–425, Jan. 2018, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2017.11.036.
- [51] I. Vigna, R. Perneti, W. Pasut, and R. Lollini, “Literature review on energy flexibility definitions and indicators for building clusters,” 2019. Accessed: Nov. 20, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://www.semanticscholar.org/paper/Literature-review-on-energy-flexibility-definitions-Vigna-Perneti/0a9fc64a83d80a15fff679a9ea2785e0ce245d90>
- [52] S. Sultan and K. Gluesenkamp, “The State of Art of Heat-Pump integrated Thermal Energy Storage for Demand Response,” Aug. 2021, doi: 10.23697/62tr-nt79.
- [53] Y. Ju, P. Hiltunen, J. Jokisalo, R. Kosonen, and S. Syri, “Benefits through Space Heating and Thermal Storage with Demand Response Control for a District-Heated Office Building,” *Buildings*, vol. 13, no. 10, p. 2670, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.3390/buildings13102670.
- [54] H. Kauko, A. Brækken, and M. Askeland, “Flexibility through power-to-heat in local integrated energy systems with renewable electricity generation and seasonal thermal energy storage,” *Energy*, vol. 313, p. 134017, Dec. 2024, doi: 10.1016/j.energy.2024.134017.
- [55] M. Singh, A. Kesselring, M. Klobasa, N. Quaresma, and A. De Almeida, “Servitization of demand-side energy services: Perspective and insights from energy service providers,” *Energy Strategy Rev.*, vol. 61, p. 101845, Sep. 2025, doi: 10.1016/j.esr.2025.101845.
- [56] J. Iria and F. Soares, “An energy-as-a-service business model for aggregators of prosumers,” *Appl. Energy*, vol. 343, p. 121487, Oct. 2023, doi: 10.1016/j.apenergy.2023.121487.
- [57] Y. Ding, D. Ivanko, G. Cao, H. Brattebø, and N. Nord, “Analysis of electricity use and economic impacts for buildings with electric heating under lockdown conditions: examples for educational buildings and residential buildings in Norway,” *Sustain. Cities Soc.*, vol. 74, p. 103253, Nov. 2021, doi: 10.1016/j.scs.2021.103253.
- [58] J. Kozadajevs, I. Zalitis, and A. Mutule, “Optimal Self Generation Portfolio for Multi-Apartment Building,” in *2024 IEEE 65th International Scientific Conference on Power and Electrical Engineering of Riga Technical University (RTUCON)*, Oct. 2024, pp. 1–6. doi: 10.1109/RTUCON62997.2024.10830901.
- [59] “Elektroenerģijas tirgus likums,” LIKUMI.LV. Accessed: Nov. 24, 2025. [Online]. Available: <https://likumi.lv/doc.php?id=108834>